

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 723974

NEWBITS

Project Acronym: **NEWBITS**
Project Title: New business models for ITS
Project Number: 723974
Topic: **MG.6.3-2016**
Type of Action: **CSA**

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

(Version 1.1, 25/10/2017)

Deliverable:	D2.3 Case study taxonomy
Work Package:	WP2: Mapping C-ITS context
Due Date:	M10
Submission Date:	27/07/2017. Resubmitted on 25/10/2017
Start Date of Project:	01/10/2016
Duration of Project:	30 Months
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
Version:	1.1
Status:	Final resubmitted
Author name(s):	Olatunde T. Baruwa, Xavier Leal
Case study contributors (leaders)	Olatunde T. Baruwa, Miquel Àngel Piera (UAB), Luciano Comelli, Leonardo Domanico, Maurizio Tomassini (TTS), Matthijs Otten (CED), Alexeis Garcia-Perez, Eleni Anoyrkati (CUE)
Reviewer(s):	Arno Schroten, Kristin Kiesow, Xavier Leal, Ivan Zaldivar, Stratos Arampatzis, Viara Bojkova
Nature:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> O - Other
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	05/02/2017	Olatunde T. Baruwa	Deliverable structure
0.2	08/05/2017	Olatunde T. Baruwa	Structure modification
0.3	12/05/2017	Olatunde T. Baruwa	Inclusion of content
0.4	16/05/2017	Olatunde T. Baruwa	Inclusion of content
0.4.1	18/05/2017	Arno Schrotten, Xavier Leal	Intermediate review
0.4.2	19/05/2017	Olatunde T. Baruwa	Structure modification
0.4.3	24/05/2017	Olatunde T. Baruwa	Methodology modification and revision/inclusion of content based on partners' comments
0.4.4	31/05/2017	Kristin Kiesow	Intermediate review
0.4.5	23/06/2017	Luciano Comelli	Inclusion of CS2 description and definition
0.5	15/06/2017	Olatunde T. Baruwa	Revision based on partners' comments and inclusion of content
0.6	07/07/2017	Xavier Leal, Matthijs Otten, Ivan Zaldivar, Luciano Comelli	Review and inclusion of content (Xavier), CS2 definition revision (Luciano), CS3 description and definition (Matthijs), CS validation (Ivan)
0.7	18/07/2017	Olatunde T. Baruwa, Alexeis Garcia-Perez	Inclusion of content
1.0	26/07/2017	Xavier Leal, Olatunde T. Baruwa	Final review. Submission
1.1	25/10/2017	Matthijs Otten, Xavier Leal	Inclusion of ACS3, edition and re-submission

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	6
Abbreviations	7
Abstract	9
0. Executive summary	10
1. Introduction	12
1.1 Background	12
1.2 The NEWBITS project	13
1.3 Objectives	14
1.4 Links to other tasks	14
1.5 D2.1 categorisation	15
1.6 Methodology	15
1.7 Overview of the deliverable	16
2. Taxonomy development	18
2.1 Taxonomy definition	18
2.2 Antecedents to taxonomies in the ITS domain	19
2.3 Taxonomy development method	22
2.3.1 Identify meta-characteristic	23
2.3.2 Identify ending conditions	24
2.3.3 Iteration 1	24
2.3.4 Iteration 2	25
2.3.5 Iteration 3	25
2.3.6 Iteration 4	25
2.4 Taxonomy dimensions	28
2.4.1 Description	28
2.4.2 Scope	29
2.4.3 Technology	29
2.4.4 Business model	30
2.5 Taxonomy application	32
3. Preselected case studies	33
3.1 Case study 1: C-ITS platform to coordinate different routers	34
3.2 Case study 2: C-ITS to manage the drivers' behaviour crossing traffic lights intersections	36

3.3	Case study 3: New ICT method to increase efficiency in logistic chain of ports (SIEEG).....	37
3.4	Case study 4: A knowledge-based approach to understanding railway safety.....	38
4.	Case study definition	40
4.1	Data gathering	40
4.2	Case study 1 definition	40
4.3	Case study 2 definition	43
4.4	Case study 3 definition	45
4.5	Case study 4 definition	47
5.	Case study validation	50
5.1	Validation criteria	50
5.2	Content validation	52
5.2.1	Case study 1 validation.....	54
5.2.2	Case study 2 validation.....	55
5.2.3	Case study 3 validation.....	57
5.2.4	Case study 4 validation.....	60
5.3	Alternative case study 1 (University VAOPoint Mobility)	61
5.3.1	Alternative case study 1 description	62
5.3.2	Alternative case study 1 definition	63
5.3.3	Alternative case study 1 validation	64
5.4	Alternative case study 3 (Synchro modal transport corridor Rotterdam- Limburg).66	
5.4.1	Alternative case study 3 description	66
5.4.2	Alternative case study 3 definition	67
5.4.3	Alternative case study 3 validation	69
5.5	Gender analysis of validated case studies	70
5.5.1	CS1 gender dimension	70
5.5.2	CS2 gender dimension	71
5.5.3	CS3 gender dimension	71
5.5.4	CS4 gender dimension	71
6.	Conclusion	72
	References	74
	Appendices.....	77
	Appendix 1 Taxonomy fiche	77
	Appendix 2 Completed taxonomy fiches of case studies	82
	Appendix 2.1 CS1 Taxonomy fiche	82
	Appendix 2.2 CS2 Taxonomy fiche.....	86

Appendix 2.3 CS3 Taxonomy fiche	89
Appendix 2.4 CS4 Taxonomy fiche	92
Appendix 2.5 ACS1 Taxonomy fiche	95
Appendix 2.6 ACS3 Taxonomy fiche	99

List of Figures

Figure 1: Taxonomy example	18
Figure 2: Part of US DoT taxonomy (Source: Gregor et al. 2016)	19
Figure 3: A 2-level taxonomy of types of developed ITS solutions developed by EC's initiatives (Source: Rafiq et al. 2013).....	20
Figure 4: Nickerson et al (2013) taxonomy development method.....	23
Figure 5: CS1 information sharing service architecture	35
Figure 6: Verona mobile app graphical interface.....	37
Figure 7: UAB pilot marketing campaign.....	63

List of Tables

Table 1: Methodology phases	16
Table 2: Taxonomy of case studies.....	27
Table 3: Validation criteria checklist.....	54
Table 4: CS1 validation report and score	55
Table 5: CS2 validation report and score	57
Table 6: CS3 validation report and score	59
Table 7: CS4 validation report and score	61
Table 8: ACS1 validation report and score.....	66
Table 9: ACS1 validation report and score.....	70

Abbreviations

APTS:	Advanced Public Transportation System
ATIS:	Advanced Traveller Information Systems
ATMS:	Advanced Traffic Management System
ATPS:	Advanced Transportation Payment System
ACS:	Alternative Case Study
B2B:	Business to Business
B2C:	Business to Consumer
CIP:	Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme
C-ITS:	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
Col:	Community of Interest
CRUE:	(Spanish: Conference of Rectors and Universities)
CS:	Case Study
CTT:	Combi Terminal Twente
CVS:	Cooperative Vehicle System
DINALOG:	Dutch Institute for Advanced Logistics
DoW:	Description of Work
DSRC:	Dedicated Short Range Communications
EC:	European Commission
ERP:	Enterprise Resource Planning
ETSI:	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU:	European Union
GA:	Grant Agreement
GPRS:	General Packet Radio Service
GPS:	Global Positioning System
H2020:	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
I2V:	Infrastructure-to-Vehicle
I2V:	Infrastructure to Vehicle

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

ICT:	Information and Communication Technologies
ITS:	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI:	Key Performance Indicator
PIARC:	Permanent International Association of Road Congresses (World Road Association)
RSSB:	Rail Safety and Standards Board (UK)
SAB:	Stakeholder Advisory Board (NEWBITS)
SIEEG:	Secure Information Exchange Extended Gate
SME:	Small and Medium Enterprise
SOA:	Service Oriented Architecture
TMC:	Traffic Management Centre
TRL:	Technology Readiness Level
V2I:	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2V:	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
WLAN:	Wireless Local Area Network
WP:	Work Package

Abstract

This report aims to create a taxonomic framework for selected ITS case studies, validate those and propose alternative validated ones if necessary, in order to ensure their relevance for implementing the tasks and analyses that will be carried out in WPs 3, 4 and 5. A structured methodological approach has been proposed such that the entire process is carried out in a reverse logical step using a 3-phase methodology. The first phase attempts to develop a 3-layer taxonomy of ITS case studies that will aid in defining the components required for market analysis and business model development. Based on empirical cases, literature analysis and synthesis, and the requirements of NEWBITS, the characteristics of ITS services are translated into a structured classification scheme. Through the taxonomic framework, case studies are then defined in the second phase according to the dimensions of the taxonomy based on the information gathered from a variety of sources. In the third phase, each case study is subjected to a content validation process to determine whether the case studies fulfil the requirements of the business ecosystem approach and in particular, WPs 3, 4 and 5. This process determines whether alternative ones need to be considered, in order to ensure that they are representative of the variety in types of the ITS market segment and service type categorisation, barriers/enablers and KPIs for the implementation of ITS services.

This report will provide a deep understanding of the selected case studies through an appropriate and accurate taxonomy. The resulting definitions will provide access to reliable information of the selected case studies, ensuring adequate support for market research analysis, development and validation of business models, and stakeholders' analysis. It could also allow stakeholders get insight into context-specific barriers and enablers affecting each case study, as well as, into the roles and participation of each stakeholder and KPIs amongst others. In this sense, the taxonomy presents the potential to be employed *a posteriori* to build the database of case studies for stakeholders interested in evaluating existing cases in order to make informed decision making.

0. Executive summary

In NEWBITS, it is highly acknowledged that the successful execution and deployment of ITS innovations involving multiple stakeholders requires efficient cooperation, interacting with each other and feeding each other with knowledge as parts of an interconnected ecosystem. In other words, the deployment of ITS initiatives should be analysed from a business ecosystem viewpoint, rather than an individual organisation perspective. This viewpoint that determines the operational level of NEWBITS is based on the business ecosystem scope given by Moore (1993) as: *the structure and behaviour of a number of organizations sharing a key platform and the set of relationships (symbiosis) between those actors.*

As the main enabler of the methodological framework of NEWBITS, case studies are considered more appropriate to gain deeper understanding of the changing conditions affecting the deployment of ITS innovations. They will ensure the feasible parameterisation of the business ecosystem concept and allow the implementation of the business modelling approach to be deployed in this project, besides the fact that they are able to provide solid evidences beyond extrapolations.

Following the results of Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2, the next step is to validate the preselected case studies and create the taxonomy of those. Although 4 case studies have been selected at the proposal stage based on a set of pre-established criteria, it was agreed at the consortium level that they are not sufficient to determine the relevance of the case studies in meeting the project's needs. This is because a validation process was not in place a priori, and also, due to the fact that the case studies have been mimicked at the proposal stage. Owing to the need to gather detailed information for these case studies in the validation process, a structured methodological approach has been deployed such that the entire process is carried out in a reverse logical step using a 3-phase methodology (taxonomy development, case study definition, case study validation). The overall objective of this report is to provide a taxonomic framework to support the validation/definition of case studies for the successful deployment of market research analysis and development of business models relying on the ecosystem concept.

Chapter 2 focuses on designing a method for collecting and validating evidences on the proposed case studies through the taxonomy. The different stages leading to the taxonomy development are described as follows. First, a general definition of taxonomy is given according to a well-accepted description from the literature, after which its importance to NEWBITS is briefly highlighted. Second, a non-exhaustive review of the existing taxonomies developed in the ITS domain is provided. Third, the taxonomy is developed in an iterative approach combining both empirical cases and theoretical concepts. Finally, the applicability of the taxonomy to other case studies is validated based on a sample case study with strong stakeholder engagement.

Chapter 3 describes the factors for preselecting the case studies in representativeness and variety, status, scalability and transferability, network of stakeholders, and market opportunities. We adopt a multiple-case approach because they allow room for cross-case analysis and comparison, generalisation and investigation in diverse settings (Yin, 2009). While there is no particular threshold, it is suggested that 4 to 10 cases are desirable for analysis in case study research (Eisenhardt, 1989, Darke et al., 1998). Based on the preselected factors, NEWBITS consortium pre-determined the number of case studies in 4,

considering the project purpose and structure, the available resources and the depth of the data collection and assessment activities to be performed. The 4 preselected case studies are further described elaborating on the initial version of the description provided in the DoW.

Chapter 4 presents a thorough definition of the preselected case studies, serving as an initial step to enable the validation process so as to ensure their usefulness throughout the lifespan of the project. The definitions are guided by the taxonomy and do not in any way involve the technical design and development of the case study. They are expected to serve as input to WPs 3, 4 and 5 by giving insight to important barriers, enablers, stakeholders' role and input, and market viability of users' needs and preferences.

Chapter 5 deploys the validation process based on content validity to determine whether the case studies fulfil the requirements of the business ecosystem approach and in particular, WPs 3 and 4. This is to ensure the alignment of their content with the project's requirements, and to ascertain the overall quality of the information obtained. The main goal is to ensure that the validated case studies fit the needs of the project. For determining the validity of the case studies, their contents were assessed against 10 validation criteria established by the consortium in line with the selection factors of the preselected case studies. Furthermore, the output of this process determines whether an alternative case study is necessary and/or additional information is required.

The first round of validation found 3 of the preselected case studies suitable, discarding the fourth due to its failure to sufficiently meet critical validation criteria such as stakeholder network position, status, data accessibility, market viability, and the existence of a strong regulatory barrier. The outcome of the first stage calls for the need to propose an alternative case study. Another round of validation was then initiated. A new case study was proposed by the CS leader by maximising their network in the field, knowing the full validation requirements as a result of the first-round evaluation. The previous steps of taxonomy fiche data collection, definition, and validation were repeated for the alternative CS. It stood out with the critical mass of end-user's involvement for the conjoint analysis to be implemented in D3.2. Other criteria were also strongly assessed to ensure its validity in achieving NEWBITS objectives.

The entire validation results show that the different aspects of the tasks to be executed in subsequent WPs have been thoroughly covered. The case studies have provided a well-balanced picture of the different transport modes (road, water, rail) and types (personal, public, freight). For each of the validated case study, a holistic intelligence process will be performed in WP3, with the subsequent WP4 deploying a network-based business modelling approach in order to provide the key to understanding the competitive environment.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

In NEWBITS, it is highly acknowledged that the successful execution and deployment of ITS innovations involving multiple stakeholders requires efficient cooperation, interacting with each other and feeding each other with knowledge as parts of an interconnected ecosystem. In other words, the deployment of ITS initiatives should be analysed from a business ecosystem viewpoint, rather than an individual organisation perspective. This viewpoint that determines the operational level of NEWBITS is based on the business ecosystem scope given by Moore (1993) as: *the structure and behaviour of a number of organizations sharing a key platform and the set of relationships (symbiosis) between those actors.*

To ensure a feasible parameterisation of key business ecosystem aspects such as the stakeholders and the relationships between them, performance, dynamics and strategies, case studies are considered as the main enabler of the proposed project methodology. According to Yin (2009) "the distinctive need for case studies arises out of the desire to understand complex social phenomena" because "the case study method allows investigators to retain the holistic and meaningful characteristics of real-life events," such as maturation of industries, for example. By so doing, stakeholders can better understand the ecosystem in which they are operating, including the characteristics that successfully affect the creation and management of the ecosystem (DoW).

The conceptualisation of the business ecosystem in NEWBITS pivots on three interrelated elements: 1. The preselection and validation of case studies, which is one of the objectives of this deliverable, 2. The CoI involving the stakeholders of the business ecosystem of each case study (WP6), and 3. The configuration of the NEWBITS Networking Platform which will be supported by the CoI (WP6). The application of the ecosystem concept is expected to facilitate the implementation of the business modelling approach, the tailored Value Network Analysis method to be deployed in WP4.

As enunciated in D2.1, the completion of prior NEWBITS tasks like the ITS categorisation and mapping exercise (published in D2.1) and the assessment of barriers/enablers (published in D2.2) are expected to bring high added value to the project at the ITS service level instead of the higher initiative level. Initiatives are too broad to understand the user preferences with regard to their needs and demands on a particular type of service. This is attributed to the high disparity of the pre-established initiative categories (as based on various difference sources of references including projects, reports, scientific papers, strategic papers...). It is therefore necessary to define case studies from a service-oriented perspective, which necessitates the need to consider context-specific cases for the deployment and provision of an ITS application through a well-defined organisational and operational framework (ITS Toolkit, 2017). At the proposal stage, four case studies have been preselected taking into account a number of factors relevant to NEWBITS objectives:

Case study 1: C-ITS platform to coordinate different routers.

Case study 2: C-ITS to manage drivers' behaviour crossing traffic lights intersection.

Case study 3: New ICT method to increase efficiency in logistic chain of ports.

Case study 4: A Knowledge-based approach to understanding railway safety.

In general, only relatively little information is known about ITS case studies. Considering the lack of relevant information, a number of knowledge-based toolkits have been implemented to provide easy and efficient access to ITS knowledge for decision-making purposes. One of such initiatives is the European ITS Toolkit (Böhm et al. 2010, Kumala et al. 2013, ITS Toolkit 2017) delivered by the FP7-funded project, 2DECIDE, which hosts the database of several ITS case studies. The aim was to provide ITS evaluation results from a decision maker's perspective including cost-benefit, impacts, user acceptance and feasibility information. According to the lessons learnt from the European ITS Toolkit, Martin Böhm warned that the shortcomings of keeping the toolkit up-to-date is partly due to the availability of quality evaluation reports and creditability of the input (Böhm 2016).

Another ongoing H2020 project ITS Observatory (ITS Observatory Consortium 2017) started in May 2015 partly aims to create a common EU-wide database that provides reliable and valuable information about the deployments, outcomes, impacts and benefits of ITS projects in Europe. The project was set forth to mitigate some of the problems encountered during the execution of 2DECIDE project (Böhm 2016). At the time of access, the database contains 19 deployed ITS projects and 1 item under category products and services covering 6 areas of ITS domains; Traveller Information, Traffic management & control, Freight & logistics, Smart vehicles, Mobility services, and Public transport.

In these databases, it is worth noting that the information available is not sufficient to help meet the needs of NEWBITS. The absence of detailed information is not only due to the fact that there is a lack of structured methods available for data collection (Stanton & Salmon 2009), but also, the lack of valid taxonomic structures for classifying information even when data is obtainable. While the structures of existing ITS databases can be adopted as a possibility to develop taxonomy, they cover much fewer categories and search criteria that could be useful for NEWBITS.

This deliverable attempts to develop a taxonomy¹ of ITS case studies that will aid in defining the components required for market analysis and business model development. Based on empirical cases, literature analysis and synthesis, and the requirements of NEWBITS, the characteristics of ITS services are translated into a structured classification scheme. This deliverable will provide a deep understanding of the selected case studies through an appropriate and accurate taxonomy. The resulting definitions will provide access to reliable information of the selected case studies, ensuring adequate support for market research analysis, development and validation of business models, and stakeholders' analysis.

1.2 The NEWBITS project

NEWBITS (New Business Models for Intelligent Transport Systems) is a Coordinated and Support Action project funded under the EC Programme Horizon 2020.

NEWBITS aims at providing a deeper understanding of the changing conditions and dynamics that affect and influence the deployment of ITS innovations. This improved understanding must contribute to minimizing the failures inherent to ITS innovation diffusion, evolve present business models, and identify effective (policy) incentives to accelerate ITS deployment.

¹ Taxonomy is defined as the science of classification, supports the transmission, clarification, and organization of large amounts of information (Gershenson, 1999). See Chapter 2 for more details.

Although the significant added value that ITS applications can provide to the European transport system has been constantly highlighted in the past years, their deployment is considered to be slow and fragmented (C-ITS Platform, 2016; Ricardo, 2016). Robust and innovative business models that would support a truly responsive approach to accelerating commoditisation and price-competition in the market for ITS services are often missing, inter alia due to the public oriented nature of ITS users (Agelidou et al., 2015). Confidence of the core stakeholders on the (long-term) profitability of their investments in ITS services and technologies is necessary and requires sound and convincing business cases.

In consideration of this global context, the project has set the following specific objectives:

1. Applying a business ecosystem's concept for ITS and C-ITS, introducing a higher conceptual level than that of individual organizations.
2. Improve the understanding of ITS and C-ITS enablers and barriers, implementing a holistic intelligence process
3. Effectively implement a network based business modelling method for ITS.
4. Validation of new business models, translation and capitalization of results.

1.3 Objectives

The overall objective of this deliverable is to provide a taxonomic framework to support the validation/definition of case studies for the successful deployment of market research analysis and development of business models relying on the ecosystem concept. The specific objectives of this deliverable are threefold:

1. To develop a taxonomy capable of providing an accurate description of case studies for the subsequent tasks to be carried out in the NEWBITS project,
2. To provide an accurate definition of 4 case studies based on the taxonomy developed in (1) in order to ensure their relevance for implementing the tasks and analyses that will be carried out in WP3 and WP4, and
3. To validate the preselected case studies and/or enable the selection of alternative ones if necessary, in order to ensure that they are relevant for the NEWBITS project and representative of the variety in types of the ITS market segment and service type categorisation, barriers/enablers and KPIs for the implementation of ITS services.

1.4 Links to other tasks

The interrelations of this deliverable within WP2 and with other WPs are described as follows. The main inputs are Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2. Overall, an inventory of 94 relevant ITS services have been identified in D2.1 at the service application level based on pilot projects and operational applications following a preceding systematisation of initiatives. These services have been mapped and categorised into different segments, according to the ITS market-by-type systems categorisation and service type. The selected services provide a well-balanced picture of the chosen ITS market categorisation. Also, the results of D2.2 will serve on the one hand to correctly identify and categorise the barriers and enablers of the case studies to be validated, and on the other hand, help in correctly defining clear KPIs for the case studies based on the KPIs identified for ITS services. This deliverable will build up on D2.1 and

D2.2 outcomes to develop an appropriate taxonomy for validating and defining the selected case studies. This is to ensure their relevance to the overall NEWBITS objectives, in particular, their suitability for the deployment of the business modelling method.

The outcome of D2.3 will be built upon by two tasks in WP3 which focus on the multi-layered market analysis on the case studies: *Task 3.1 Market research analysis and Task 3.2 Perform conjoint analysis to analyse user preferences on the case studies*. Thereafter, WP4 will be dedicated to the development of innovative business models for the selected case studies in D2.3 to better understand the business ecosystems in which specific ITS services are developed and applied, while WP5 will formalise and generalise the lessons learnt from the business models of the case studies towards the ITS domain. Finally, the concept of the Communities of Interest (CoI) in WP6 will serve as an enabler of the network-oriented business modelling approach to be performed on the validated case studies.

1.5 D2.1 categorisation

Two levels of categorisation have been presented in D2.1; the first considers the broad spectrum of ITS services according to the market segment by type (classified into five market segments - ATIS, ATMS, ATPS, APTS, CVS), while the second is defined as a bundle of services called “*service types*” based on a number of key criteria such as enabling technology, communication, TRL, primary benefits in addition to the market-by-type segmentation. The latter was formed as a result of their clustered segmentation behaviour on the mapping results performed on the selected ITS services in the inventory collected in D2.1.

In this deliverable, we have considered only the market-oriented categorisation of ITS services due to the fact that the service type categorisation offers a streamlined perspective of a selected number of ITS services, and also, some of the service types do not fit into the objectives of NEWBITS. For instance, Type 1 service is composed of services at TRL = 9, which must be excluded owing to the fact they are already in the market and have been supported by a well-defined business model. Therefore, they are not relevant to the project since case studies to be considered must be linked to close-to-market and on-going initiatives.

1.6 Methodology

To achieve the aforementioned objectives, a three-phase methodology is proposed (Table 1); (1) Taxonomy development, (2) Case study definition, and (3) Case study validation.

In the first phase, the taxonomy of case studies is developed based on empirical cases and theoretical concepts, as well as the requirements of WPs 3, 4 and 5. The resulting taxonomy tree is further validated with a sample empirical case to ascertain its applicability to a larger number of case studies. The generated taxonomic framework will serve as the basis for further implementation of the data gathering and definition processes of cases in Phase 2, and the validation of those in Phase 3.

In the second phase, the preselected case studies are defined based on the taxonomy dimensions. A thorough analysis is then performed to provide a better understanding of the cases considering the data quality and usability for WPs 3, 4 and 5. For each case, a detailed data gathering is performed by the responsible case study leader employing different methods of data collection such as information search on the web/project documents and semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders.

After an in-depth analysis of the preselected case studies, the third phase involves the validation of the case studies against the categorisation results of D2.1 and D2.2, and the requirements of WPs 3, 4 and 5. This is to ensure that they are of high relevance to the project. The rationale for validation is based on content validity of the definitions from the taxonomy, given a number of validation criteria defined by WPs 3, 4 and 5 leaders. Some of the criteria to perform the validation includes; data accessibility, willingness of the stakeholders to participate in the case study, market viability, and potential for market uptake and replication.

Phase	Steps	Tools	Results
Phase 1: Develop taxonomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify relevant dimensions, characteristics, and objects for initial taxonomy development. Run through several iterations of the taxonomy-development method until all characteristics are validated. Validate taxonomy. 	D2.1 inventory of ITS services for empirical data, D2.2 assessment of barriers/enablers and KPIs, desk research for theoretical concepts, sample empirical case study, taxonomy development method	Taxonomy of case studies
Phase 2: Case study definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gather data on preselected case studies. Define case studies using the taxonomy developed in Phase 1 	Information search on the web/project documents, semi-structured interviews with stakeholders, taxonomy tree	Taxonomy definition of preselected case studies
Phase 3: Case study validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up rationale for validation. Perform qualitative assessment and content validity of case studies. Request additional information where necessary. Reconsider other case studies if representative objective is not met. 	Validation criteria (D2.1, D2.2, WPs 3, 4 and 5), content validity for cross-check validation	Validated case studies

Table 1: Methodology phases

While Phase 1 is standalone and serves as input to the other phases, Phases 2 and 3 are interdependent and can as well be executed in a closed-loop fashion. This is such that Phase 2 is deemed to be complete when the data gathered has been assessed to be sufficient for the validation process in Phase 3, and/or the case definition meets the validation criteria. For example, if additional information is needed to reassess a case study during the validation phase, the responsible case study leader is asked to gather more information for the case study redefinition as set out in Phase 2. In a situation where a preselected case study does not meet the validation requirements, an alternative case study will be proposed relying on the capability of the partner to maximise her network. Phases 2 and 3 are then repeated for the alternative CS until it is found suitable.

1.7 Overview of the deliverable

The remainder of the deliverable is organised as follows. Chapter 2 focuses on designing a method for collecting and validating evidences on the proposed case studies through the taxonomy. Then, the factors for preselecting the case studies are described in Chapter 3

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

followed by brief descriptions. The cases are further defined in Chapter 4 based on the taxonomy, after sufficient information has been gathered. In Chapter 5, the case studies are subjected to a content validation process by analysing their contents and providing an evaluation report for every case study to assess their overall quality. Furthermore, the output of this process determines whether an alternative case study is necessary and/or additional information is required. Finally, Chapter 6 concludes the report by giving a summary of the work done.

2. Taxonomy development

This chapter describes the different stages leading to the taxonomy development. First, a general definition of taxonomy is given according to a well-accepted description from the literature, after which its importance to NEWBITS is briefly highlighted. Second, a non-exhaustive review of the existing taxonomies developed in the ITS domain is provided. Third, the taxonomy is developed combining both empirical cases and theoretical concepts. Finally, the applicability of the taxonomy to other case studies is validated based on a sample case study with strong stakeholder engagement.

2.1 Taxonomy definition

Technically, a taxonomy T as defined by Nickerson et al. (2013) is a set of n dimensions, D_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$), each consisting of k_i ($k_i \geq 2$) mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive characteristics C_{ij} ($j = 1, 2, \dots, k_i$) such that each object under consideration has one and only one C_{ij} for each D_i . Given this definition, let us assume a taxonomy example is a hierarchical structure that can be arranged in three layers (Figure 1). The dimensions can be found at level 1, with each dimension having a defined number of characteristics/categories in level 2, and every characteristic containing a number of attributes in level 3.

Figure 1: Taxonomy example

In NEWBITS, the taxonomy will be used to identify the key inputs to support the definition of case studies and to ensure their relevance in the execution of tasks to be performed in WPs 3 and 4. The definitions resulting from the taxonomy could allow stakeholders get insight into context-specific barriers and enablers affecting each case study, as well as, into the roles and participation of each stakeholder and KPIs amongst others. In this sense, the taxonomy presents the potential to be employed *a posteriori* to build the database of case studies for stakeholders interested in evaluating existing cases in order to make informed decision making.

2.2 Antecedents to taxonomies in the ITS domain

Due to its wide application in several fields, taxonomy has attracted a lot of interest. Taxonomy development is either focused at a broader classification scheme at the domain level or for specific applications of narrower topics within the domain. For example, Remane et al. (2016) develop a taxonomy for car sharing business models in which the proposed classification scheme serves to fulfil a number of functions; to transform the technological advancements in car sharing into the creation of economic value, to provide a more accurate analysis of existing car sharing operators, and to systematically discover new business models. Along this line, Labes et al. (2013) propose a cloud business model taxonomy to analyse IT service providers' business models.

Although there have been extensive studies in different domains, not many works have been conducted on taxonomy development in the ITS domain. Existing taxonomy approaches of related studies in smart city and city logistics (Benjelloun et al., 2010, Perboli et al., 2014) focus on high-level initiatives at the macro-level. In the ITS domain however, most initiatives are perceived to deploy one or more services (Deliverable 2.1). A number of taxonomies have been developed for the ITS domain.

- The U.S. Department of Transportation's research (RITA US DoT, 2015) developed a taxonomy of the ITS field considering several Levels of Detail (LoD), as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Part of US DoT taxonomy (Source: Gregor et al. 2016)

- Rafiq et al. (2013) propose two taxonomies of EU ITS projects and initiatives under the FP6 and FP7 funding schemes. The first describes a 2-level taxonomy of selected EC initiatives/projects classified into 4 areas of interest; CooperativeMobility, EcoMobility, SafeMobility, and InfoMobility. The second is another 2-level solution-oriented taxonomy of the types and application areas of the ITS solutions proposed by the projects (Figure 3).

These taxonomies are mostly based on application areas. For the purpose of defining case studies however, application area is just one of the many categories to be considered in the taxonomy.

Figure 3: A 2-level taxonomy of types of developed ITS solutions developed by EC's initiatives (Source: Rafiq et al. 2013).

Taxonomy can also be derived from existing ITS databases. Structures used by ITS Observatory include: *Country*, *ITS domain* (Smart vehicles – Connected and Automated Vehicles – Public Transport – Public Transport Priority Management – Road Transport Personal Safety - Safety enhancement for vulnerable road users/disabled road users/ In-vehicle safety equipment), *Geographical coverage*, *Area of transport* (Public Transport/ Other (cycling)), *Problem area/objective*.

The ITS Toolkit uses a 4-dimension taxonomy to search for evaluation reports of case studies (El-Araby et al., 2010), and an additional 4-dimension in the output (Technical, Legal/Regulatory, Financial, Business model):

1. User context
 - a. Geographical coverage (Europe, Nation, Regional, Urban)
 - b. Area of transport (Passenger, Freight, Transport Infrastructure)
2. Goals, objectives
 - a. Travel efficiency (reduce congestion, improve traveller information, reduce travel time...)
 - b. Road safety (reduce accidents, manage accidents effectively)
 - c. Improve public transport service (improve accessibility to public transport services, improve public transport monitoring and operations, improve public transport traveller information...)
 - d. Improve freight management (improve freight management, improve truck parking, manage urban freight...)
 - e. Improve freight fleet management (improve fleet management)
 - f. Enhance Security (improve planning for/mitigation of natural disasters, increase feeling of security for travellers, improve prevention/detection of crime, vandalism, terrorism...)
 - g. Reduce environmental impacts
 - i. reduce transport emissions (CO, NOX, particulates...)
 - ii. improve local air quality
 - iii. reduce noise
 - iv. reduce greenhouse gases from transport

- v. optimize energy consumption
- h. Improve road traffic planning, operations
 - i. improve traffic management (cross-border, organizational co-operation)
 - ii. improve traffic data (better detection and processing)
 - iii. improve traffic estimation and forecasting
- i. Improve revenue generation
 - i. introduce/improve road user charging
- j. Decrease traffic violations
 - i. improve monitoring and enforcement of violations
 - ii. improve back-office management of enforcement
 - iii. improve compliance rates
- 3. Problem
 - a. Congestion/capacity issues in road transport
 - i. congestion on roads due to: incidents
 - ii. special events (e.g. trade fairs, sport events, ...)
 - iii. road works
 - iv. weather
 - v. regular congestion (recurrent)
 - vi. low travel time reliability
 - b. Parking issues
 - i. parking availability
 - ii. parking information
 - c. Accidents
 - i. accidents/black spots
 - ii. weather-related problems
 - iii. slow/imprecise/unreliable incident detection
 - iv. poor incident response and clearance
 - v. high number of secondary incidents
 - d. Traveller Transport Services
 - e. Noise and Air Pollution
 - f. Freight transport
 - g. Violations/Security
- 4. ITS Service (adapted PIARC Classification)
 - a. Traveller Information Services
 - b. Traffic Management and Operations
 - c. Intelligent Vehicle Services
 - d. Freight Transport Management
 - e. Public Transport
 - f. Emergency Services
 - g. Electronic Payment
 - h. Road Transport Personal Safety
 - i. Weather and Environmental monitoring
 - j. Disaster response management and co-ordination

Overall, the categories used for these databases may not suffice to support the development of business models. They are missing important criteria (such as market viability, stakeholder interaction, costs etc. (see Chapter 2.3)) considered necessary to perform market analysis as well as to enable the development of specific business models (the business ecosystem

approach) as proposed by NEWBITS project. Notwithstanding, the ITS Toolkit provides an interface to search for ITS case studies; however, the information provided is quite limited to allow the deployment of the business modelling approach in this project. Besides the KPI identification being included in the database of the ITS Toolkit, most taxonomies have not covered key factors such as barriers and enablers for assessing business models and policy incentives.

2.3 Taxonomy development method

A comprehensive literature survey in (Nickerson et al., 2013) classified taxonomy approaches into three categories; inductive (empirical, Labes et al., 2013), deductive (theory or conceptualisation, Perboli et al., 2014), and intuitive (ad-hoc).

In this study, we employed a well-accepted approach to taxonomy development (Nickerson et al., 2013) that combines two strategies (conceptualisation/deduction and empiricism/induction) into a single method in an iterative manner to allow for the flexibility in getting the best usable taxonomy.

Our aim is to develop a taxonomy of NEWBITS case studies by answering the following questions:

- Can we find the relevant dimensions/axes that categorise the different characteristics of ITS case studies for the deployment of the business ecosystem concept briefly described in the introductory section?
- Can the relevant criteria identified in D2.1 and D2.2 fit into these dimensions?
- Is the information required for the taxonomy tree obtainable from the case studies?

To come up with relevant dimensions, the following factors are taken into account:

1. The identification of relevant concepts in the NEWBITS context. The relevant requirements are focused on market analysis, stakeholder analysis, users and their preferences (need and demand), and the value network analysis.
2. The analysis of the ITS services identified in D2.1.
3. The categorisation of the list of criteria² identified in D2.1 and D2.2 under their respective dimensions.
4. The analysis of the criteria used by similar works on ITS taxonomy in the literature.

In this light, we will build on previous results by:

- Focusing on key components of ITS services described in D2.1 and D2.2, and expand previous classifications wherever applicable to ensure their relevance within NEWBITS and the ITS domain, and

² D2.1/D2.2 criteria list: Technology maturity, ITS enabling technology, Targeted geographic deployment area, Transport mode, Type of transport, Primary benefits, Institutional framework, Stakeholders, Transferability, Barriers, Enablers

- Analysing previous taxonomy works of city logistics and smart city projects (Benjelloun et al., 2010, Perboli et al., 2014) in order to describe ITS case studies.

According to Nickerson et al (2013), the development of taxonomy involves determining the characteristics of the objects of interest. In this method, the taxonomy development steps consist of 4 unique steps with the third step involving an iteration of 2 distinct cycles (Figure 4). The first step is to identify the meta-characteristic, a super characteristic that serves as the basis of the choice of characteristics in the taxonomy, the possible set of dimensions. The second step is to outline the ending conditions. The third step determines the approach to follow, which iterates over two different cycles that allows dimensions/categories to be added or removed. One of the cycles is the empirical-to-conceptual that employs an inductive approach using empirical cases to identify subset of objects to be classified/grouped under some dimensions in the taxonomy. The other is the conceptual-to-empirical cycle that engages a deductive approach to identify dimensions and characteristics from a sound conceptual/theoretical foundation/literature. This is then followed by the analysis of a real-world case study to examine the characteristics and dimensions obtained. Finally, the method is finalised when the ending conditions are met.

Figure 4: Nickerson et al (2013) taxonomy development method.

The application of the method is demonstrated in the following Sections for the development of the case study taxonomy.

2.3.1 Identify meta-characteristic

The first step is to identify the meta-characteristic, understood as a super characteristic that covers the possible choice of characteristics in the taxonomy. The meta-characteristic is based on the purpose of the taxonomy. Here, the purpose is to provide an accurate description of ITS

services to enhance the understanding of the case studies for a thorough market analysis and deployment of a network-oriented business modelling approach (VNA).

The resulting meta-characteristic then becomes the market and business modelling characteristics that support the definition of value network analysis of case studies. The taxonomy components are based on the potential use of the taxonomy defined by the requirements of WPs 3 and 4 (see Chapter 1.4). As a result, the characteristics to classify must explicitly conform to WPs 3, 4 and 5 needs. Potential users are WPs 3/4/5 leaders. Thus, the development becomes straightforward since we already know the purpose it will serve.

2.3.2 Identify ending conditions

Ending conditions states the conditions (objective and subjective) that must be met before the development can be terminated. We applied 3 objective and 5 subjective ending conditions from Nickerson et al. (2013). The objective conditions are:

- The taxonomy must have the right number of dimensions with exhaustive characteristics,
- All possible characteristics have been added and at least one object is classified under every characteristic of every dimension, and
- Every dimension is unique, and so must every characteristic be unique within its dimension.

The subjective conditions include: conciseness, robustness, comprehensive, extendibility, and explanatory.

2.3.3 Iteration 1

In constructing taxonomies, a number of different dimensions can be defined. The focus is to develop the taxonomy on dimensions relevant to NEWBITS needs. Under each dimension, several categories are identified which are considered to describe the various substantial aspects that are representative of the dimension. While a dimension can be expected to have many categories (an exhaustive list of categories) depending on the context, the categories defined in each dimension are selected/limited based on requirements of the NEWBITS work packages and the needs of the project.

First, we opted for an empirical-to-conceptual iteration. Since the case studies will be validated on the outputs of D2.1 and D2.2, our first taxonomy was developed based on the defined long list of criteria (see Footnote 2). The data fiche used to collect data for ITS services provided a first guide to identify the characteristics common to the empirical cases in the inventory. Initially, three dimensions are defined in the fiche: Description, KPIs/barriers/enablers, and Impacts. The characteristics common to the ITS services are specified under each dimension. The groupings are done using a manual process based on a similarity notion among the related characteristics.

Some of the proposed characteristics that turn out not to be relevant are eliminated from further analysis, such as status and country. Applying the ending conditions, we noticed that some of the characteristics have been grouped under the wrong dimension. This necessitated the need for a revision.

2.3.4 Iteration 2

This iteration conceptualises the dimensions from existing works on the taxonomy of related ITS cases in the literature using the conceptual-to-empirical path. We conducted a search in the scientific literature for taxonomy of ITS case studies. Apparently, there is no work directly dealing with the topic, but we were able to identify two relevant papers on Smart City and City Logistics projects (Benjelloun et al., 2010, Perboli et al., 2014) where ITS play a vital role for smart transportation systems in urban environments.

Relevant dimensions identified in the literature contain most of the characteristics that have been identified in Iteration 1. However, the classification of the characteristics into dimensions proposed in Iteration 1 was not consistent with those from the literature that have dealt with empirical cases as we were unable to obtain a match, except for the *Description* dimension. Thus, the previous dimensions are eliminated and a new set is generated. The new dimensions are: *Description*, *Scope*, *Technology*, and *Business model*. Characteristics are reorganised, and the objects are examined for the identified characteristics and dimensions to ascertain their appropriateness. Also, we ensured that the taxonomy contain dimensions that are mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive.

The empirical case analysis of this conceptualised stage is left to a later stage (see Chapter 2.5) for a comprehensive evaluation of all the characteristics and dimensions. At the end of this step, we determined whether the ending conditions have been met by cross checking with the subjective and objective conditions. There are still question marks raised over the comprehensiveness of the taxonomy.

2.3.5 Iteration 3

No doubt, the previous deliverables and the literature analysis in iteration 2 have provided to an extent, detailed information required to complete the taxonomy. However, they do not suffice to support the other work packages. In this regard, the aim of this iteration is to ensure that the requirements of WPs 3 and 4 are sufficiently addressed in the taxonomy.

At this iteration, there is no longer a need to conceive new dimensions. All the relevant dimensions were validated at the 2nd PMB meeting by the consortium. At this point nonetheless, new characteristics may be needed, and we decided to take on the empirical-to-conceptual iteration. The partners raised concerns at the PMB meeting on its validity to cover the different aspects and requirements of WPs 3, 4 and 5. There is a need to fine tune the previous version.

The leader of this deliverable (UAB) maintained continuous communications with WPs 3 and 4 leaders (ATOS and ORT) to ensure that the criteria used align with their requirements and needs. A revised version of the taxonomy was then developed taking into account their comments and inputs. Several characteristics were added under the business model dimension; stakeholder interaction, costs, timing, and market type. In particular, the “type of stakeholders” objects were redefined. At this point, the taxonomy seems to be on course, but we felt that special attention needs to be given to the business model dimension because of its importance in the NEWBITS project.

2.3.6 Iteration 4

This iteration is meant to fine-tune the business model dimension. The conceptual-to-empirical approach is used by conducting desk research on business model taxonomies. At the business

model category, only the criteria related to financing (both operational and management) has been considered in the previously analysed literature. For specific business models such as the value network analysis, it is quite imperative not only to dwell on the financing aspects, but also, the roles, inputs, and outputs of each stakeholder in the deployment of ITS services.

The business models in this case where a business ecosystem involving multiple stakeholders and interaction among them, goes beyond only cost and revenue models/operation financing. The essential components of business models defined in Labes et al. (2013)'s taxonomy is used to capture the relevant categories. The 5 components described in this work are covered in our taxonomy, which includes: business strategy (market entry, market strategy, diversification), value proposition (product, services, provisioning model...), value creation (partner network, resources and activities, costs), and value delivery (target market, distribution and customer relationship, revenue).

The aim is to formulate/identify the necessary inputs/characteristics required for the development of each business model component. For example, the cooperation entity subcategory of partner network in Labes et al (2013) has 4 attributes (ecosystem, strategic alliance, loose cooperation, purchase), but we have only considered the possible inputs to the ecosystem cooperation (the NEWBITS working approach) such as stakeholder interaction that describes the role, needs, input, output, and type. The partner type under the same category has been taken care of under the description dimension. The same measure applies to the other components like business strategy where we have considered the barriers/enablers to market entry. With this iteration, the characteristics of the business model dimension were reorganised and further regrouped by the business model components. This makes the dimension a 4-layer taxonomy.

Based on this method, a three/four-level taxonomy of case studies was developed, as shown in Table 2. We consider it appropriate and sufficient to enable the definition of case studies after testing the objective and subjective conditions. For the final test, we examine the usefulness of the taxonomy in Chapter 2.5, which is further subjected to discussion at the 3rd PMB meeting in Thessaloniki.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Dimension		Characteristics	Attributes						
Description	Objectives	Safety	Efficiency		Comfort		Environment		
	Innovation Level	Deployed	Close-to-market		Emerging		Pilot		
	Innovation type	Incremental	Differential		Radical		Breakthrough		
	Type of stakeholders	Government	Public authorities	Industry/ITS associations	European Commission	Academia	End users	Others	
	Project initiator	Public	Private			Public-private			
Scope	Transport mode	Unimodal (air, road, rail, water)			Multimodal				
	Transport type	Personal		Public			Freight		
	Geographic coverage	Urban		Motorway			Corridor		
	Purpose	Road safety	Traffic management		Freight services	Parking	Routing	Vulnerable road user	
Public Transport		Environmental Protection		Aut.Telematics	Road user charging		Automated Vehicles		
Technology	Communication	Short range		Long range		Hybrid			
	Sensing	Radar		Camera		Road side beacons			
	Hardware	Central		Roadside		Personal		Vehicle	
	Decision	Algorithms			Simulation				
Business Model	Value proposition	Product	Tangible			Intangible			
		Infrastructure financing	Public	Private			Public-private		
	Value Creation	Operation financing	Public	Private			Public-private		
		Management of network	Public	Private			Public-private		
		Stakeholder grouping	Role	Objectives		Needs		Input	Output
		Stakeholder interaction	Human resources	Monetary	Policy	Goods/Services	Technology	Knowledge	Others
		Cost structure	Tangible costs and minimum resource needs			Intangible costs and minimum resource needs			
		Target market segment	ATIS	ATMS		ATPS	APTS	CVS	
	Value Delivery	Type	B2B	B2C			Others		
		Revenue model	Revenue stream		Price targets			Profit margins	
		Impacts	Economic		Social		Environment		
		KPIs	Deployment			Benefit			
	Business strategy	Timing	Short term		Medium term		Long term		
		Market viability	Need		Demand			Acceptability	
		Barriers	Institutional	Economic	Technical	Organisational	Social and attitudes		Impact
Enablers		Institutional	Economic	Technical	Organisational	Social and attitudes		Impact	Other

Table 2: Taxonomy of case studies.

2.4 Taxonomy dimensions

This section presents the dimensions of the taxonomy and their respective characteristics and attributes. Overall, the taxonomy has 29 characteristics and 114 attributes.

2.4.1 Description

Description aims at defining the context and main features of the case study using 5 criteria:

- Objectives: This characteristic aims at describing the objectives of the case study and the problem addressed. It is expected to indicate all the primary benefits of the ITS services offered in terms of safety, efficiency, comfort or environment (D2.1).
- Innovation level: An ITS service may be in different stages of development. According to the TRL (D2.1), this criterion describes the innovation phase (deployed, close-to-market, emerging, pilot) of the services in order to assess their maturity.
- Innovation type: According to the following definitions given by Kadareja (2015), the type of innovation is specified in terms of the degree of novelty:
 - Incremental: Incremental changes to existing products, projects that are typically focused on line changes or improvements in a firm's existing product offerings.
 - Differential: New products for the same markets, moderately innovative products for existing markets.
 - Radical: New products for new markets.
 - Breakthrough: New products that create new markets that usually refer to revolutionary change in firms, markets and industries, which provide substantially higher customer benefits relative to current products in the industry.
- Project initiator: This criterion describes the sector that launched the case, whether it is a private sector (one or more enterprises), public sector (city or government) or a mix between the private and public entities.
- Type of stakeholders: Several stakeholders may be involved in ITS project development and execution, each with its own role, needs, objectives and interests. This is necessary to correctly map the participating stakeholders for the analysis to be performed in the network business modelling approach. The following stakeholder groups have been identified:
 - Government: This consists of the 3-tiers of government; national, state, and city/local, and may also include provincial government.
 - Public authorities: This group comprises government agencies at all levels (national, state, and city/local) such as infrastructure managers, regulatory body, transport authority, roads authority...
 - Industry/ITS associations: Examples of entities under this group include: OEMs, ITS service providers, ICT service providers, suppliers, Transport operator, Road operator, ITS association
 - European Commission
 - Academia: This comprises universities and research institutes.

- End users: These are citizens or businesses that are consumers of the ITS service.
- Others: This group comprises stakeholders not already defined under the above-mentioned groups. They can be specialised media, social media marketing companies, international partners (outside the EU) etc.

2.4.2 Scope

This dimension indicates the area, deployment environment, and transport type covered by the ITS service in the case study including its final goal. This classifies the case study according to 4 criteria:

- Transport mode: This criterion determines whether the service offered is unimodal (road, rail, air, water) or multimodal.
- Transport type: This criterion determines the type of transport covered by the ITS service, such as personal, public, and freight.
- Geographic coverage: The geographic coverage refers to the type of areas where the ITS service is mainly applied (in urban areas, on motorways, or corridors) for the road/rail transport mode.
- Purpose: ITS services can serve different purposes in improving road safety (e.g. road work warning systems), providing routing (travel) and traffic advices. Other purposes include: traffic management, freight services, vulnerable road user (pedestrians, cyclists, and persons with disabilities or reduced mobility) applications, public transport, environmental protection, automotive telematics, road user charging, and automated vehicles.

2.4.3 Technology

The technology dimension describes the key enabling technologies supporting the deployment of ITS services. This has already been explained in detail in D2.1 with a reference to the 8 technology blocks proposed by TTRANS project (2013).

- Communication: This consists of short range (Wireless Local Area Networks (WLAN); Dedicated Short-Range Communications (DSRC) systems (ITS G5), 802.11p WAVE, Wi-Fi), long range (Cellular networks/WAN (GPRS (2G), 3G, 4G), positioning (GPS satellites)) or hybrid (a combination of short and long range) communication technologies.
- Sensing: This includes video cameras, radar, and road-side beacons.
- Hardware: This refers to hardware such as central (centralised traffic management system), roadside (beacons, poles, smart traffic lights...), personal (mobile phones, tablets, personal navigation devices, and other hand-held devices) and vehicle (hardware installed in the vehicle to enable communications (V2V, V2I)).
- Decision: This describes decision technologies (software-based systems) used for the design, analysis, planning, management, and control of the ITS services. Algorithms and simulation are some of the decision-support tools often used in the ITS domain.

2.4.4 Business model

This dimension covers the 4 key components of the business model framework as given in Labes et al. (2013). The characteristics are thought out to be the main inputs for describing each of the component.

Value proposition: This component entails the description of the product/service (whether tangible or intangible) offered to fulfil end-users' needs.

Value creation: Focuses on the inputs required to determine how the stakeholders create value within the contexts of the networks they operate

- Infrastructure financing: This is used to describe the main financing sources/providers of the infrastructure, whether it is provided by the city/government (public) or private firms or the ownership is shared between public and private entities.
- Operation financing: This determines whether the execution of the project is sponsored by public funds, private entities or co-funded/joint collaboration between public and private entities.
- Management of network: ITS innovations usually require the collaboration of different stakeholders. This characteristic determines how the network is governed. By a public body, if it is 100% publicly funded. By a major stakeholder that is a private company and dominant on the market, the so called a private dominant leadership. And thirdly, by an equally integrated private-public partnership.
- Stakeholder grouping: For each stakeholder in the network, the following attributes are used to collect and analyse qualitative information to determine whose interest should be taken into account when developing or implementing an action.
 - Role: This describes the stakeholder main activities/role in the network.
 - Objectives: This describes the main purpose of the stakeholder and his interests.
 - Needs: What the stakeholder may need to reach his objectives.
 - Inputs: What the stakeholder uses [or could use]/receive from other stakeholders.
 - Outputs: What the stakeholder produces and is [or could be] used by other stakeholders.
- Stakeholder interaction:
 - Monetary interaction: When there are monetary transactions exchanged between stakeholders.
 - Human resource interaction: Training of personnel and exchanges of such training within the network.
 - Policy interaction: When there are policy-making contributions and exchanges of policy documents between stakeholders, particularly between public authorities and other stakeholders.
 - Technology interaction: When there are exchanges of technology equipment/kits between stakeholders.
 - Knowledge interaction: When there are exchanges of knowledge between stakeholders.
 - Others: Any other type of interaction not described with the above-mentioned attributes.

- **Cost structure:** Describes the various cost items/expenses of the case study. This includes any financial information the stakeholder is willing to share. It could be costs from their daily operations (operational costs), costs from the infrastructure used in their activities, investment costs etc. as relative to the case study.
 - **Tangible costs and resource needs:** This includes financial investments or operating capital, time and materials, facilities and equipment, projects at different stages of implementation, market barriers for implementation etc.
 - **Intangible costs and resources:** This includes R&D activities, high-end skilled workforces, human skills and competence, business relationships, brand-identity, media relations, lobbying activities, incentives to innovate (enablers), advertising and management structure, etc.

Value delivery: Focuses on the characteristics needed to deliver the value proposition such as the different customer groups, channels for distribution, customer relationship, impacts including the revenue generated from the product.

- **Target market segment:** The target market can be divided into 5 segments (ATIS, ATMS, APTS, APTS, CVS) according to the market-by-type categorisation from D2.1 based on its characteristics, behaviour and requirements.
- **Type:** This entails the type of commerce strategy in the case study.
 - **B2B:** ITS services/products of a business marketed/sold to other businesses.
 - **B2C:** ITS services/products are marketed/sold to the final consumer by the business.
- **Revenue model:** Financial information the stakeholder can share about the main sources of their income, where they receive their money from, and profits. This can range from licensing, usage fee, subscription fee, advertising, third party sponsorship, donation etc.
- **Impacts:** This is used to quantify the impacts realised by the case if any in economic, social, or environmental terms.
- **KPIs:** This describes the extent to which the ITS service meets its defined objectives – expected impact. These are KPIs used to evaluate the case study according to D2.2 categorisation:
 - **Deployment KPIs:** As defined in D2.2, they are related to the extent by which ITS services are implemented. Examples include the percentage of road network using various types of ITS services and the percentage of vehicles with intelligent vehicle features (AECOM, 2015)
 - **Benefit KPIs:** As defined in D2.2, they are related to the (desired) impacts of ITS services. Examples include the percentage change in journey times, accident rates or CO₂ emissions along routes once ITS have been implemented (AECOM, 2015)

Business strategy: This describes some peculiar characteristics on the strategic alignment and goals of the case studies.

- **Timing:** The timing of the case study, whether short term, medium term, or long term.
- **Market viability:** Describes the market vision by identifying the market needs and demands.
 - **Need** – To identify potential users and their interests. According to TTRANS project (2013a), *need is a detected requirement that in the future (in short or*

medium term) will be demanded by the market, but at this moment is not “necessary” to provide the current services or functionalities in the sector.

- Demand – According to TTRANS project (2013a), *demand is a requirement requested by the market to improve their solutions, is an expectative that the market expects with more or less urgency to enrich the services.*
- Barriers: Describes the main barriers of the case study according to the categories defined in D2.2 (Institutional, Economic, Technical, Organisational, Social and attitudes, Impact, Other).
- Enablers: Describes main enablers of the case study according to the categories defined in D2.2 (Institutional, Economic, Technical, Organisational, Social and attitudes, Impact, Other).

2.5 Taxonomy application

From the steps taken in the taxonomy development, we have employed conceptualisation approaches by identifying new dimensions and characteristics from the literature (in Iterations 2 and 4). In order to ascertain their usefulness in the real world, the analysis of an empirical case through a sample case study is deemed necessary to crosscheck the taxonomy. This is to ensure that the proposed taxonomy can be used for classifying the information of other case studies. It can also be useful in detecting any missing components in the taxonomy.

To evaluate whether the taxonomy characteristics and attributes meet the desired objectives, i.e. for definition of case studies, the taxonomy was cross-checked after consultations and interviews with the stakeholders of a sample case study. This is to check whether the required inputs can be obtained directly from the stakeholders and other sources such as project documents. In particular, the Verona case study from the COMPASS4D project was used due to the involvement of one of the partners (TTS) in the execution and deployment of the project. At this stage, the stakeholders of the sample case are engaged in the information provision to ascertain the extent to which data is accessible. The outcome from the interaction with the stakeholders and the completion of the taxonomy dimensions determined the usefulness of the proposed taxonomy for NEWBITS needs.

3. Preselected case studies

Case studies are considered a key enabler of the methodological framework of NEWBITS due to the fact that they are able to provide solid evidences beyond extrapolations through the rich and in-depth description of data which can enable the discovery of theory (Misuraca, 2010) where existing knowledge is limited (Cavaye, 1996). According to Yin (2009), "*A case study is an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between object of study and context are not clearly evident*". The role of case studies in NEWBITS is considered more appropriate to gain deeper understanding of the changing conditions affecting the deployment of ITS innovations. To achieve this aim, it is therefore highly important that case studies are carefully selected so as to suit the purpose of the project, in the particular case of NEWBITS, the definition of new business models.

As already indicated in the DoW and further elaborated in D2.1, the key factors taken into consideration in the preselection process are the following:

- **Representativeness and variety:** Case studies must be representative of key business areas of ITS by the market segment categorisation and at the same, offer varying characteristics encompassing the 4 modes of transport. This is to avoid a generalisation of a particular business area to another one without a priori understanding of the business area under study.
- **Status:** Case studies must comprise projects having a certain level of maturity; can either be ongoing, piloted, or deployed.
- **Scalability and transferability:** Case studies must have potential for scalability to enhance the system by adding new functionalities as well as replicability/transferability to other regions.
- **Network of stakeholders:** Case studies have to enable the definition of a network of stakeholders, facilitating knowledge sharing and fulfilling the premise of a value network
- **Market opportunities:** Case studies have validated potential to nurture a new or recreated operating leverage proposal or growth-market opportunity, which could be adapted to the existing business environment or extrapolated to other business ecosystems.

In a case study-based methodological approach, the number of cases to be considered typically depends on the focus of the project and the context in which it is applied. We adopt a multiple-case approach because they allow room for cross-case analysis and comparison, generalisation and investigation in diverse settings (Yin, 2009). While there is no particular threshold, it is suggested that 4 to 10 cases are desirable for analysis in case study research (Eisenhardt, 1989, Darke et al., 1998).

Based on these factors, NEWBITS consortium pre-determined the number of case studies in 4, considering the project purpose and structure, the available resources and the depth of the data collection and assessment activities to be performed. A recurrent discussion during WP2 implementation has been around the possible need to increase this number in order to add

robustness to the overall project approach. After having advanced in the assessment of the categorization (D2.1) and enablers, barriers and KPIs (D2.2), and moreover, counting with enhanced and more comprehensive information about the processes to be deployed in the core tasks of the project (in WP3, WP4 and WP5), the resolution from NEWBITS consortium is to keep the number as originally established in 4 cases. Besides ensuring the adequate deployment of the project method, the consortium has strongly considered the need to deploy the business ecosystem conceptualization (based in the 4 case studies and the Communities of Interest around those) following a rational scope given the resource limitations existing in the project. This decision has been consolidated during the 2nd Work progress and PMB Meeting held in Thessaloniki during the second week of June.

The 4 preselected case studies are further described in the following sections elaborating on the initial version of the description provided in the DoW.

3.1 Case study 1: C-ITS platform to coordinate different routers

Motorway bottlenecks usually are considered emergent dynamics that cannot be predicted. This fact is partially right when being caused by an accident or an incident between vehicles, however when caused by over demand, instead of emergent dynamic, bottlenecks should be considered un-modelled dynamic. This case study presents a new initiative that aims to deploy a centralised information management platform in a collaborative framework in order to coordinate different route planners for solving the capacity-demand balance of road freight transport. The new service (Figure 5) relies on enhancing commercial ITS solutions with the cooperation capacity to:

- Predict over-demanded zones: Road freight transport companies use fleet planners to generate the “optimal route” to each truck. At present, this information is relevant only for the transport company, however the causal analysis of these isolated routes is an excellent source of information to identify and predict over-demanded zones and its interdependencies.
- Mitigation mechanisms: A demand-capacity balance mechanism to suggest time-stamp changes or re-routing options under a reward mechanism to transform “queuing” by “waiting” truck operations.

The service will be complemented by a tracking functionality for real-time advice issuance, but also to improve the robustness of the solutions. This new service should be implemented considering fairness, transparency and equity criteria to engage freight transport companies in this cooperative ITS framework.

A review of commercialised routing and mapping ITS software reveals that software programs are mainly designed to optimize the routes of individual trucks or fleets. Despite the performance benefits that can be obtained at company local targets, the lack of cooperative capacity of ITS software constrains the potential benefits that could be obtained by the evolution of V2I S/W (i.e. Routing and mapping products) to I2I. Thus, the main focus is to satisfy company transport demands trying to avoid the assignation of all trucks to routes, contributing in this way to mitigate some known distribution inefficiencies such as:

- Low load factors and empty running
- High number of deliveries made to individual premises within a given time period

- Long dwell times at loading and unloading points

A similar initiative has already been deployed in the aeronautical domain called System Wide Information Management (SWIM 2017). SWIM is an aeronautic domain new cloud and cooperative driven ITS platform developed to coordinate airline routes considering the airspace capacity.

The analysis of this case study will include: lessons learnt from other city logistic ITS routing aimed at optimizing logistics operations in an urban environment (taking into account the infrastructure urban capacity and the benefits and costs for all stakeholders (Taniguchi et al. 2003)), relevant research and innovation done at the EU level in the deployment of new routers oriented to particular KPIs (Smartfusion, Reduction, FURBOT, SATURN), and the cost of development and deployment of SWIM as a similar C-ITS approach in the aeronautical.

This approach opens a new market in which router cooperation/competition mechanisms could support new routing solutions in which transport costs would be reduced considerably. Currently, present routers do not interact at all. They only receive time-space constraints to avoid bottlenecks. The application of NEWBITS business modelling methodology towards the C-ITS focused router uptake opportunity is expected to pave the way for maximizing the high potential of the SWIM approach towards the road domain, identifying new business models that support the introduction of a change in the trend in carrier-shipper relationships, moving away from a transactional framework to a relational one. Overall, this is a case study that could garner interest from different stakeholders ranging from municipalities, transport authority, road traffic operators, freight transport operators to ITS service providers.

Figure 5: CS1 information sharing service architecture

3.2 Case study 2: C-ITS to manage the drivers' behaviour crossing traffic lights intersections

This case-study refers to the ITS applications implemented over the past 10 years in the city of Verona, with particular reference to the activities of the EC Compass4D project. Verona is located in the Veneto region, northern Italy, with approx. 265.000 inhabitants. It is the second largest municipality in the region.

In order to improve urban mobility, based on the EC's agenda in relation to national strategies for ITS directives, the Verona City Administration has moved in the last decade to provide solutions to the new challenges that have emerged in recent years regarding Climate Change, Energy Policy, Air Quality Legislation and difficulties in Addressing Congestion Phenomena. In October 2008, the city of Verona joined the Alliance of Mayors, sponsored by the EC in the framework of the Sustainable Energy Campaign in Europe; then in April 2011, it adopted an Environmental Energy Plan which contains guidelines and strategic goals in the energy sector; and then in October 2011 approved the Action Plan for Air Quality and Remediation, with structural measures for counteract air pollution and pay particular attention to mobility. As a result, Verona city introduced a traffic management platform in the traffic management centre (TMC) where autonomous ITS systems and applications exchange data and are coordinated by a higher-level subsystem. Such a system included OMNIA, an ITS platform that supports an open architecture where any ITS system can be integrated within the platform, independently of the supplier product or technology. This system acquires all the traffic measures and stores it in the central system archive together with their estimated statistical profile such as traffic volumes, speed, etc. and traffic related data (e.g. signal plan, clearance capacity, turning proportions etc.). More than 150 intersections in Verona were connected with this platform. The system also included MISTIC, an Info mobility platform or Town Supervisor for cooperative traffic monitoring in the traffic management centre (TMC), and UTOPIA, a traffic management control system that provides adaptive traffic control strategies. Moreover 33 variable message signs in the urban were implemented for parking info (urban), traffic info and collective routing.

With the subsequent Compass4D pilot application, started in 2013 and developed into an EU CIP framework, part of the city, in particular the main corridor and arteries, has been equipped with a cooperative RSU system, made up of 25 ETSI 5G compliant units, OBUs for various vehicles, and some cameras for the safety application. Moreover, a web application has been developed for mobile devices, allowing an increasing number of users access to numerous mobility data. The web service has been provided through 4G communication service (for "day-one" C-ITS application), through the collaboration with the national telecom operator and project partner, Telecom Italia.

Due to this implementation, new services have been provided to users: Speed Advisor System (GLOSA system), Road Hazard Warning (RHW) service, and Red light violation function. Also included in the service bundle is the implementation of Transit Signal Priority service. Figure 6 depicts the graphical interface of the mobile app used in Verona as the long-range communication option to provide ITS services to users/drivers.

Figure 6: Verona mobile app graphical interface

3.3 Case study 3: New ICT method to increase efficiency in logistic chain of ports (SIEEG)

The project name of the case study is SIEEG, standing for Secure Information Exchange Extended Gate. The SIEEG project has been initiated by the Combi Terminal Twente (CTT) to improve the security and efficiency of container transport from the deep-sea terminal (Rotterdam) to the Hinterland via CTT. Within the SIEEG project, a platform has been created that enables the different stakeholder in the chain to share and retrieve relevant information on the transport chain. In addition to stakeholders sharing data, sensor technology has been applied to generate additional trustworthy information. At the inland terminal, sensors enable secure and efficient registration of truck drivers and containers. The SIEEG platform enables different stakeholders in the transport chain to align their actions.

SIEEG was a demonstration project in 2011-2014 sponsored by the institute DINALOG. At the moment, the functionality is still used by CTT and partners.

By aiming at the creation of an efficient extended gate functionality in Hengelo (border Germany) for the port of Rotterdam with the same service level (security, customs) as in Rotterdam, the SIEEG case study relies mainly on two aspects:

- Transport efficiency
- Secure transport service

The demonstration project has shown that the SIEEG resulted in time reduction of gate entry by trucks at the inland terminal, an increase in container transport by inland waterways to the inland terminal and improved exchange of information between partners.

The analysis of this case study will include lessons learnt from the pilot. The application of NEWBITS business modelling methodology is expected to pave the way for maximizing the high potential of the case study for transferability to other inland terminals.

3.4 Case study 4: A knowledge-based approach to understanding railway safety

This case study addresses the need to use experts' knowledge when analysing data to inform decision making in the railway industry. The project was structured in two phases:

1. Phase 1. Theory development (2013-2014): focused on developing a method for eliciting knowledge from experts and use that knowledge in data analysis;

Phase one was based on the challenges derived from the availability and increasing nature of a vast range of data within the British railway industry as a result of uninterrupted data collection processes across the industry. At this stage, the project explored the feasibility of using the data available within the railway industry to inform new mechanisms to assure safety and security of customers, staff and the public in an industry where the interdependence between physical and digital environments is set to grow exponentially over the next few years. This phase of the project delivered a small-scale solution which served as a proof of concept for a safety predictive tool. Using knowledge elicitation techniques, and involving leading industry and academic safety experts, the project created a series of models of railway data and safety, and the developed a metadata-driven, safety-focused model of railway operation and performance; a prototype software tool that uses metadata models for the prediction of safety-related faults was also developed.

2. Phase 2. Pilot, practical implementation (March 2017-present), consists of an implementation of the method in practice, an initiative funded by Network Rail to turn every train into an infrastructure monitoring train. The initiative is funded by the H2020 project entitled 'Transforming Transport' under the topic: [ICT-15-2016-2017 - Big Data PPP: Large Scale Pilot actions in sectors best benefitting from data-driven innovation](#). Network Rail who is a partner on this project, has been investing private funds to enable a pilot based in the UK which is partially run by Coventry University.

On completion of its first phase, the approach to data analysis developed by KEEP SAFE were adopted by one of the initial partners to run a pilot study on how to turn every train into a monitoring train. The new project focused on the collection and analysis of infrastructure data to inform decision making. The new phase, currently underway, becomes both a validation of the method initially developed and a solution of a practical problem the railway industry is facing: improvement of the infrastructure monitoring mechanisms to support predictive maintenance and provide a better and safer service to the public.

4. Case study definition

A thorough definition of the selected case studies serves as an initial step to enable the validation process so as to ensure their usefulness throughout the lifespan of the project. The definitions are guided by the taxonomy and do not in any way involve the technical design and development of the case study. They are expected to serve as input to WPs 3 and 4 by giving insight to important barriers, enablers, stakeholders' role and input, and market viability of users' needs and preferences.

4.1 Data gathering

The collection of case study data can be difficult and time-consuming as highlighted by Cavaye (1996), especially when several stakeholders are involved. The developed taxonomy in Section 2 serves as a guide to obtaining data on the variables of interest for the case studies, upon which they will be defined. It is worthy to note that a complete definition will require a thorough data collection for it to be deemed useful for analysis in the subsequent WPs, essentially addressing most of the characteristics under each dimension. The lack of precise information can create biased models which can otherwise become ineffective in the long-term.

The method of data (source) triangulation (Stake, 1995) is adopted where multiple sources of data are used to collect evidence on the case studies in order to increase the precision of the collected data. One of such methods is conducting interviews directly with the relevant stakeholders involved in the project. Another method is desk research by consulting different documentations ranging from project documents available on the internet or the project website, annual reports to scientific literature

A case study information leaflet was developed by CE Delft with the aim to inform the stakeholders of the case studies on the benefits from their participation and how they can support the NEWBITS project in terms of data provision, workshop attendance and participation in the Col. Case study leaders are responsible to contact and conduct semi-structured interviews with the relevant stakeholders (whenever applicable) in order to provide more in-depth and informed information. Some of the key stakeholders of the 4 preselected case studies are already part of the SAB. A taxonomy fiche (Appendix 1) is developed to aid the data gathering process. Appendices 2.1 to 2.4 present the information collected in each case study through the taxonomy fiche. The resulting definitions of the case studies are provided in the following sections according to the 4 dimensions of the taxonomy.

4.2 Case study 1 definition

Description: CS1 intends to offer an information sharing service in a competitive/collaborative framework in which a capacity/demand tool will suggest:

1. Routing time-stamp changes preserving confidential business model information at the tactical level, and
2. Mitigation mechanisms issuing real-time routing advice to freight transport companies/truck drivers at the operational level/real time when new bottlenecks would emerge.

This collaborative idea that is jointly initiated by an SME (Aslogic) and a logistics research unit of the UAB has the primary objective of predicting over-demanded zones and suggesting alternate slots for planned routes at the tactical level. This in turn is expected to improve efficiency in terms of energy and level of service, as well as reduce environmental issues (CO₂ and pollutant).

The project proposes a breakthrough innovation in road freight transport, since it introduces a new service that can be applied at different geographical levels and implementing different reward policies for the freight transport system. It is worthy to mention that CS1 is currently at the conception stage. However, reaching a pilot level is not far off because it will rely on existing commercial decision support tools that must be enhanced with a web service to match the information and feedback time constraints under a consensus reward mechanism.

It is envisaged that CS1 would need about 11 stakeholder groups consisting of government, university, transport operators, ITS service providers, road operators, transport authority, roads authority, ICT service providers, end-users, and a funding body like the EC to support implementation and deployment of the solution proposed. To reach a critical mass, a regulatory body is needed because new regulations are required to enhance the use of the service.

Scope: Although a similar service already exists in the aeronautical transport mode, CS1 focus is on road transport with a target geographic coverage of motorway. Service could be applied at regional, national or European level. The main control will be on freight transport in which personal transport demand will be considered passive. A future extension of the project could consider also personal transport. It is expected to serve five purposes:

- Traffic management: Tactical demand-capacity balance.
- Freight services: Reduction of the travel time by mitigating the number of bottlenecks caused by a spatio-temporal concentration of trucks in one area.
- Routing: A passive mechanism for routing interoperability.
- Environmental Protection: Reduction of the amount of CO₂ impact and fuel burning.
- Road user charging: New reward mechanisms will be considered as a mechanism to reach a critical mass of end-users.

Technology: The service will employ long range communication channels (3G/4G and GPS tracking) for issuing real-time routing advice and tracking respectively. Also, a service oriented architecture (SOA) with a peculiar data exchange protocol to support the flow of data with different routers distributed in other systems or central units. Camera will be used for monitoring purposes in real time. In terms of hardware, a centralised traffic management system will be deployed to compute at tactical level spatio-temporal constraints to be issued to freight transport companies under a fairness and equity policy. Also, in a situation of constraint violation, end-users will be notified to take some corrective decisions through personal hardware such as mobile phones, tablets, personal navigation devices, and other hand-held devices. Decision algorithms will be used to analyse freight transport demand shared by routers together with traffic patterns to identify bottlenecks and its interdependencies. Simulation on the other hand will be used to predict the effects of the mitigation mechanisms and to support transparency among end-users.

Business model: The system will offer a cloud service (intangible) in which routers will connect through SOA mechanism. Infrastructure wise, the full system could be implemented could be supported by private financing. The monitoring capacity with road cameras would however require public financing. At technological level, it is not envisaged an important risk in the implementation, however, benefits will depend on the critical mass and the policies implemented. No private companies would like to take the implementation risk if stakeholder engagement is not guaranteed.

The management of the network can be controlled solely by private entities, but policies implemented for the mitigation mechanism should be a consensus between private-public partnerships. The main value flows amongst stakeholders will be based on 3 key interactions; 1. Policy: Capacity-demand policy requires of smart win-to-win policies that should allow end-users satisfy their own transport hard-constraints (i.e. delivery time) while adapting routes considering soft-constraints (delivery sequences), 2. Knowledge: Different traffic patterns will require different mitigation mechanism making it essential to collect previous expertise when issuing capacity constraints, and 3. Trust: A regulation policy could benefit some private companies while penalizing others. To really succeed with the proposed service, a transparency mechanism should be provided to truly be engaged in the system.

The target market segments include ATIS, ATMS and ATPS. The commerce strategy can be B2B where ITS services that can be sold to router developer and ERP companies, and B2C where ITS services can be sold to freight transport companies. The case study is a medium-term business such that once deployed, it is expected that 1 or 2 years is sufficient to reach the critical mass in order to measure real benefits.

Europe re-industrialization has been recognised as a market need which can equally act as an enabler. This re-industrialisation as emphasised by Lirzin & Schramm, (2012) requires of new efficient road surface transport infrastructure, in which transport time and cost should be reduced to competitive values. The minimization of motorway bottlenecks through information sharing platform and small time-stamp or re-routing adjustments seems to provide the right solution envisaged by traffic authorities and drivers.

One of the main challenges to piloting and deploying the solution is institutional, as new policies/regulations will be required for pricing (tolls), usage, and compliance. Also, the lack of cooperation between stakeholders needs to be dealt with, given that private freight companies competing in the same market should start cooperating under a win-to-win approach. Another barrier that could come into play is interoperability (technical) between the different route planners, since the information required by the service still needs to be agreed upon and defined without affecting the business model of the participating freight companies. Economic barrier can become an issue as the initial stage for pilot study would require public funding.

At the moment, some key components of the business model cannot be fully determined due to the fact that stakeholders are yet to be fully engaged in the deployment of the service. These are: cost structure, revenue model, market viability (demand, acceptability), impacts, and KPIs. Although in revenue terms, it is envisaged a price target mechanism sold under a pay-per-use policy complemented with a public subsidiary compensation according to benefits measured.

4.3 Case study 2 definition

Description: The case-study objectives rely mainly on three aspects: safety issues, efficiency (energy, level of service) and environmental issues (reducing CO₂ and pollutant). These objectives are intended to be pursued by improving the urban traffic performances, through improving driving behaviours and control systems, thanks to a specific cooperative-ITS system implementation.

New services in the city of Verona consisted in Road Hazard Warning (RHW), Road Works Warning, Speed advisory (GLOSA system), Red light violation warning and, finally, a Transit speed improvement through signal priority (TSP).

The RHW System aims to prevent collisions in case of abnormal or blind queues, and Road Works Warning aims to prevent similar circumstances. Speed Advisory instead aims to improve driving behaviours due to prevent vehicles stopping at red lights: the objective is to smoothen the traffic stream, reducing energy consumption and pollution, but also improving mean speed while reducing peak speed which can be useful also to improve road safety; moreover, the same technology is useful to prevent red light violations, but also to detect it. Finally, the system also provides for transit signal priority (TSP), which can be seen as an additional service oriented to transit operator that can be translated into further benefits for the final users.

The implemented solutions are easy to replicate thus the project exhibits a close-to-market innovation, which also has the characteristics of a radical innovation. The project indeed introduces new services and implements for the first time in Italy a cooperative-ITS solution. It was initiated under an EU CIP co-financing, with the central role of the Municipality of Verona.

The project involves various stakeholders' categories: a public authority (the Municipality of Verona), an Urban Transit operator, Taxis operators, Citizens, an automotive supplier (Audi), an Original Equipment Manufacturer (SWARCO MIZAR) and an ICT service provider (Telecom Italia). The relations with transport companies involved in the pilot were maintained primarily through Verona Municipality. SWARCO MIZAR was the point of contact for all technical issues related to Verona pilot, providing updated status information about the overall project to the City and additional Transport Companies. Face-to-face meeting with local stakeholders were organized with monthly frequency in Verona. The Decision-Making Process scheme has been designed to the explicit aim of including citizens and all the stakeholders in decision activities.

Scope: The project focus is on the urban road transport mode, with the primary involvement of private users and public transport users as secondary. Given the urban nature of the service, the geographic coverage is limited to the city of Verona, with the project serving the purposes of road safety and traffic management/improvement.

Technology: The ITS application into this case study relies on cooperative-ITS category, involving I2V communications, whilst the adoption of specifications and standards and Vehicle-to-Vehicle communications are not in the scope of the project. Moreover, it is important to highlight that the implementation of a 4G communication service (for the "mobile" long range communication option) is the first case in Europe for an ITS service.

Communications in this case are based on cooperative-ITS real-time messages that can both run on short-range and long-range communication systems, since two parallel communication options are provided.

Short-range communication option runs between roadside units (one for a single junction) and on-board-units (OBUs), and is based on ETSI-G5 standard (a 5Ghz Wireless LAN standard for ITS application). This option provides Traffic Information, Traffic lights Assistant and Road Works Warnings information. In particular, the Traffic Light Assistant uses SPAT/MAP standard for encoding and broadcasting information about junctions' topologies and regulation parameters, while event-related information, such as Traffic Information and Road Works Warning, uses instead a CAM-DEMN format to broadcast information to vehicle.

Long-range system is based on a 4G platform which links the central unit (TMS) and the users' mobile devices (which have to run a specific software app): In-vehicle information reach the driver with a delay <3s.

System central unit is also capable to use DATEX protocol to exchange data with other systems or central units.

Focusing on hardware, the system is made of a Central unit, various Roadside units (≥ 25), some Short-Range type Driver G5-OBU (Audi self-equipped vehicles, buses, other vehicles....) (≥ 20), and various Long-Range type Driver units: common mobile devices/tablets with specific software app.

Business model: The implementation targets Advanced Traffic Management System (ATMS) and Advanced Traveller Information System (ATIS) market segments. The final products are tangible. Generally, they produce services for the final end-users, but the Transit Signal Priority system is particularly aimed at public transport operators.

The management of the system, in any case, is fully public, in charge to Verona Municipality. In this sense, the relations with transport companies involved in the pilot were maintained primarily through Verona Municipality. SWARCO MIZAR was the point of contact for all technical issues related to Verona pilot, providing updated status information about the overall project to the city and additional transport companies.

Focusing on economic analyses, it has to be highlighted that initial investment cost has been reported as € 360.000, while annual operational cost has been estimated as € 24.000. Since the project was carried on under an EU CIP co-financing, it required 50% of costs covered by the local public beneficiaries.

Based on such evaluation, the annual minimum revenue was estimated in € 68.384,74: this is the amount that would allow the service to run without any monetary loss, making the Net Present Value (NVP) of the service for a period of 10 years equal to zero. The Annual minimum revenue was intended to be guarantee through environmental and energy benefits monetization.

Evidenced impacts are generally positive, since the implementation resulted in Stops reduction (15%, simulated data), Travel time reduction (-7%), road Safety improvement and Energy consumption and Environmental emissions reduction (smoother driving behaviour can be translated in this result).

Regarding the emissions reduction, some considerations are exposed in the following. The annual passenger travel time and CO₂ emissions for Verona are ex-ante estimated in 22594 hours per person per year and 63610 tons/year of total CO₂. Considering that the societal cost of CO₂ emissions is 120€/ton, the equivalent of the

estimated minimum annual revenue of € 68.384 is roughly 570 tons of CO₂. This represents approximately 0.9% of the annual CO₂ emissions of the City of Verona at the time of the pilot, and this number could be interpreted as the reduction of CO₂ emissions that could make sustainable the project just from CO₂ emissions point of view.

Environmental benefits have been proved thanks both to direct measurements and simulation: while direct measurements have been carried on during one year, collecting data from both vehicles and intersections, unfortunately these data resulted not fully suitable to a precise evaluation of pollutant emissions reduction, requiring some strong-assumption-based interpolation. The simulation application was driven through different scenarios considering various sensitive parameters (penetration rate, communication delay, traffic demand) in order to determine the impact of the services on both drivers (travel times, fuel consumptions, number of stops) and municipality (traffic flow).

The services have shown to be accepted and well evaluated by users, since they allow to improve safety and mean speed, and to reduce drivers' stress.

Regarding barriers and enablers, the main barrier resulted to be essentially operational, and it regarded privacy issues related to communications. During the Compass4D pilot, indeed, a large amount of data has been collected in order to evaluate benefits of the system: some of the data will potentially need to identify vehicle and/or the driver. The raw data has been treated as confidential and collected and organized in databases allocated according to inter-operational standards (DATEX II, ETSI, etc.). On the other side, the Municipality participation have been very important, showing to be experienced about European projects, and this fact acted as a clear enabler. Other evidenced driver was that the city was yet equipped with ITS applications, such as OMNIA platform controlling more than 150 junctions, and other systems/technologies (for urban traffic control, etc.).

4.4 Case study 3 definition

Description: In the SIEEG demonstration project (2011 -2014), a platform has been created that enables to share information of sensors, and between stakeholders in the transport chain from deep sea terminal Rotterdam via inland terminal CTT to the hinterland. The goal of the project was to create an extended gate functionality in Hengelo (border Germany) for the port of Rotterdam, with the same service level (security, customs) as in Rotterdam. The technology has proven itself and is used by CTT and partners.

The primary objectives of the SIEEG project were to increase transport efficiency and security through the inland terminal of CTT. Other objectives include the increase of profitability for stakeholders, the use of sensor technology, the creation of public extended gate functionality and an increase in the attractiveness of inland waterway transport.

The project proposes a differential type of innovation. The container transport efficiency on an existing link is improved. The innovation of the project is the establishment of a secure information extended gate functionality, using integrated and synchronized data exchange between terminals and shippers through an open IT platform.

The project involves various stakeholders. It has been supported by TKI Dinalog, an institute based on public-private partnership that aims to boost innovation in logistics in the Netherlands. TKI Dinalog has financed the research and had a monitoring role in the project. The initiator of the project was Combi Terminal Twente (CTT), an inland terminal in Hengelo,

the Netherlands. Project partners were two logistics service providers, another inland terminal, the University of Twente and IT service providers. Other (indirect) stakeholders are shippers, truck drivers, skippers, port authorities, and customs as they all play a role in transport chain.

Scope: SIEEG focus is on road intermodal transport (road and inland waterways, potentially also rail) on the link Rotterdam- Hengelo-Hinterland. It serves the following purposes:

- Increased efficiency of container transport from deep sea terminals to the hinterland; saving time and costs and releasing pressure on the road system around Rotterdam.
- Higher security at inland terminals.
- Increase of profitability for stakeholders.
- Use of sensor technology to increase the exchange of better and more trustworthy information in the hinterland chain.
- To create a public extended gate with the best available infrastructure for a secure lane.

Technology: SIEEG is a web-based service that allows logistics agents to share and monitor data about handling and transportation of goods. To improve the communication through the SIEEG platform the following technology is applied:

- At the inland terminal GPS is used to have trucks automatically report to the terminal; geofencing (long range).
- The truck registers through optical character recognition and hand scan.
- Ship movements are followed by public AIS data (long range).

The hardware consists of a server with the standardized communication platform for data exchange communication, GPS systems in the trucks, AIS on inland waterways ships, Optical character recognition (OCR) for identification of cargo and a hand scanner for truck driver identification.

Business Model: The value proposition is an intangible web service system to share the transport information between stakeholders in the transport chain. The project is initiated and financed by private partners, supported with a research budget by TKI-Dinalog (public-private institute). The total budget of the project was € 1,172,00, of which € 250,000 funded for research by Dinalog. The objectives and needs of stakeholder differ. Trip and planning information, security information and profitability are the main value flows. Stakeholders interact by sharing the logistics information, by coordinating planning consequences between employees at stakeholder operational level (human resource interaction) and by sharing knowledge on the development and operation of the SIEEG platform.

The target market segments include ATIS, and types of ATMS and ATPS, while the commerce strategy is B2B. The main impacts of the project are shorter transport times on the link Rotterdam-Hengelo-Hinterland, higher security and higher inland waterway transport volumes through CTT to the hinterland. The improved transport efficiency and security are key for the revenue model. Some important KPIs are: created jobs, effectiveness of data sharing, increase

of high value goods volume, transshipment time of trucks at the terminal, and CO₂ reduction on the link Rotterdam-Hengelo.

The demonstration project run from 2011-2104. The SIEEG functionality is now in use by CTT and partners. As deep sea ports, like Rotterdam face road capacity problems on the routes to the hinterland, inland ports are interesting alternatives to use inland waterways and rail to divert some of the deep-sea port road traffic to inland locations. Other inland ports have already shown interest in the SIEEG concept to increase the service level of inland ports.

One of the main barriers identified by the SIEEG project partners was heterogeneous data formats of the information of the partners and the hardware components installed. The biggest challenge in the project was to synchronize the information of these components properly, taking into account the legacy software solutions that were used. Technical knowledge and perseverance of project partners have been important enablers for the project.

4.5 Case study 4 definition

Description: A vast range of data exists within the railway industry, and their availability continues to increase as a result of uninterrupted data collection processes across the industry. The initial phase of this project, which ran between 2013 and 2014, explored the feasibility of using the data available within the railway industry to inform new mechanisms to assure safety and security of customers, staff and the public in an industry where the interdependence between physical and digital environments is set to grow exponentially over the next few years.

The project delivers a small-scale solution which serves as a proof of concept for a safety predictive tool. Using knowledge elicitation techniques, and involving leading industry and academic safety experts, the project has created a series of models of railway data and safety, and has developed a metadata-driven, safety-focused model of railway operation and performance; a prototype software tool that uses metadata models for the prediction of safety-related faults has also been developed.

On completion of its first phase, the outcomes were adopted by one of the initial partners to run a pilot study on how to turn every train into a monitoring train. The new project focused on the collection and analysis of infrastructure data for the purpose of informing decision making. The new phase, currently underway, become both a validation of the method initially developed and a solution of a practical problem the railway industry is facing: improvement of the infrastructure monitoring mechanisms to support predictive maintenance and provide a better and safer service to the public.

Thus, the findings of this project support decision-making in relation to a number of areas within the railway as a system. The project had an impact in practice and theory in a number of additional areas including infrastructure reliability, security of railway-related information systems, prognostics, predictive maintenance and human factors.

Scope: The project focuses on rail transport. As a method, it does not have a specific target geographic coverage. However, the pilot study that followed the development of the method has been focused on a particular section of the railway network within the UK, namely the London-North West route.

Passenger trains vehicles are considered. It serves three overarching purposes:

- Infrastructure management: Fault prognostics and predictive maintenance
- Customer safety: Reduces the risk of accidents due to system failure
- Business performance: Reduces disruptions caused by unplanned maintenance and repairs

Technology: The project relies on two main technologies which serve the following purposes:

- Data collection and secure storage. Sensors are placed on trains to capture V2I data, which is data related to the interface between the train and the railway network, e.g. overhead electrification. The data is then transmitted from the train to a secure server at Coventry University using the Internet.
- Data analysis and visualisation: Using among others the approach initially developed by KEEP SAFE, the data is analysed using experts' views and the outputs are fed back to the industry in a visual form for inspection and decision making.

Business model: The value proposition consists of a system which allows railway infrastructure owners to collect raw data and turn it into a visual artifact. Such visual representation of the data is informed by experts' knowledge and therefore enables engineers to identify areas where potential failure modes are being developed and plan for their timely repair. This is supported by an Information Technology infrastructure which is in this case best placed at the University. This approach brings into the railway industry part of the experience gained by other transport domains such as the aerospace.

The commerce strategy here is mainly B2B, based on the different stakeholders within the provision of railway transport, in this case in the UK. Although still in development, impact has been positive as it shows the enabling capability and potential impact on the business and its customers, as the reduction in unexpected disruption and repair has a direct impact on costs saving, reputation etc.

Some important KPIs are: number of issues detected/corrected in advanced, potential cost (economic or otherwise) of an issue not having been detected, engineers time saved, disruptions avoided. These KPIs are linked to the project's main objectives:

- Improve the safety of rail workers by minimising the time spent trackside.
- Improve the safety of rail passengers by identifying trends toward asset failure.
- Improve the reliability of services by minimising downtime and service interruptions.
- Improve cost efficiency by prioritising preventative maintenance on assets based on a number of factors.
- Improve service capacity by minimising disruption.

In terms of market viability, the pilot is being co-funded by Network Rail as the owner of the British railway infrastructure. This means that the initial beneficiary of this solution is the British railway industry and its customers. However, the problem is not endemic to the UK and therefore the solution may well serve other countries within Europe and beyond.

The main barriers to market entry include the cost of the process of collecting data from trains, given that it implies modifications to the infrastructure to fit sensors. The risks involved are data

alignment problems (different data sets collected from separate areas)-unable to confirm correlations, access to data in a timely fashion, unable to distinguish between root cause and symptoms, insufficient asset specialist input into requirements and review of output

The principal enabler for the market is the cost-saving associated to this solution. Other drivers are; economic (high cost of disruptions), regulatory (the need to meet regulations which set standards to be met in terms of quality of service, safety etc.), technical (a technology that can be expanded to cover other systems and subsystems within the railway infrastructure), and other benefits such as reputation, increasing demand of the railway service, move towards a digital strategy in the next decade etc.

5. Case study validation

For a case study-based approach, some of the problems encountered are concerns over validity and reliability (Yin 2009). A recent experience of the 2DECIDE project (Bohm 2016) acknowledged the creditability of the input as an important issue to deal with. Martin Bohm further highlighted that “a proper quality control needs to be put in place to guarantee credible, reliable and quality information”.

While 4 case studies have been preselected at the proposal stage, they are required to be validated to ensure their suitability and relevance in meeting the project’s needs and implementing the successive tasks linked to WP2. In general, validation concerns whether a product meets the requirements and needs of customers and stakeholders. Here, it is to be determined whether the case studies fulfil the requirements of the business ecosystem approach and in particular, WPs 3, 4 and 5.

It is worth mentioning that some criteria have been used to preselect the case studies as described in Section 3. While these factors provide a reasonable path for preselection, the consortium agreed that they do not suffice to determine the suitability of the case studies for achieving the project’s objectives. A compelling reason for this is owed to the fact that the case studies have been mimicked at the proposal stage. This raises the need to gather more information on the case studies in Chapter 4 beyond the ITS application area, technology, market segments, barriers/enablers and KPIs.

The taxonomy has provided the framework for the identification of the data available on selected characteristics of interest for the preselected case studies, as well as their definitions. Based on this, the assessment of the case studies can then be performed. The validation process will take into account the following as already highlighted in the taxonomic framework in Chapter 2:

- The defined categorisations on market segments published in D2.1.
- The defined categorisations on barriers/enablers, and KPIs published in D2.2, and
- WPs 3, 4 and 5 requirements. WPs 3, 4 and 5 leaders were asked to elaborate on the expected goals, needs, criteria and conditioners for a case study.

5.1 Validation criteria

Given the three-underlying validation rationale for the assessment of the case studies, the consortium has established 10 evaluation criteria in line with the selection factors of the preselected case studies.

1. **Network of stakeholders:** Case studies have to enable the definition of a network of stakeholders, as essential premise to knowledge share facilitation and ultimately value network at the specific case study level. At this stage of the project implementation, the business ecosystem is simplified towards a potential value network, considering basically the existence of a number of actors whose efforts are focused on addressing specific needs of a given end-customer or user.

2. **Willingness of the stakeholders to actively participate:** Following the initial factor, obtaining the participation of the stakeholders is considered paramount to the analysis of the case studies. It has already been indicated in Darke et al. (1998) that most businesses and other organisations have not always shown the willingness to participate in case study research. Case study leaders are tasked to ensure the willingness of the stakeholders in their respective case studies to participate in the diverse activities programmed in the project towards the fulfilment of the network business modelling. Some stakeholders' interest has already been confirmed by means of letter of support at the proposal stage. To encourage the participation of others, communication from the case study leaders has been focused on highlighting the benefits to participate in WP3 and WP4 activities, and how the insights gained can be of value to their organisations.
3. **Data and documentation relevance and accessibility:** This criterion relies on the second factor. The key requirement being that there is sufficient information available and stakeholders can support (and ideally ensure) access to it. Sufficient information is needed to support the execution of diverse tasks to be performed on the case studies in the course of WP3 and WP4, such as market research analysis and value network analysis. Stakeholders should be willing to give information needed, including to a very limited extent, potentially sensitive commercial information. NEWBITS consortium intends to limit the need for such data by establishing clear boundaries in the required inputs for cost structures and revenue models. The aim is to have significant data to allow valid analyses, but at a level that does not compromise by any means each organisation competitive approach. The consortium relies on establishing a trusted relationship amongst the partners and the stakeholders involved. This enabling element has been considered since NEWBITS inception at proposal stage and will be constantly reinforced.
4. **Market segment:** As introduced in prior sections of this document, Deliverable 2.1 presented a level of categorisation considering the broad spectrum of ITS services according to the market segment by type (classified into five market segments – ATIS, ATMS, ATPS, APTS, CVS). In order to be considered relevant for the purposes of the project, it has been established that each case study must cover at least 2 of the 5 market segments.
5. **Market viability:** NEWBITS case studies are ultimately required to embed potentially innovative or novel business models. In order to increase the relevance factor of the modelling, case studies must contain market viability information and/or a pre-assessment of the market potential. That information has to be considered positive, so as to align the potentiality of the cases (market wise) with the expected impact of the projects. This element is even more critical considering the need to reduce the risks of pursuing non-viable propositions while circumscribing the project tasks to a limited universe of case studies (4).
6. **End-user involvement:** The assessment of the market situation of the case studies by considering users' preferences will be implemented in the conjoint analysis to be performed in WP3. The underlying logic for the introduction of the conjoint analysis as market research method is the need to acknowledge the increasing role of end-users in the innovation process. NEWBITS considers the sum of actions performed by users

in the ecosystems as essential elements to enable value co-creation and innovation diffusion. NEWBITS case study must clearly identify end-users as one of the main stakeholders. In consideration with the conjoint needs for a significant critical mass (so to perform the analysis under valid parameters), it is considered that at least **2 of the validated** case studies have **citizens** as end-users.

7. **Technology:** As stated in Deliverable 2.1, technologies and technology based categorizations are helpful in the ITS domain given its complexities. It is also a required step to consider the technology maturity of the services. In this sense, the criteria agreed is that each case study must cover at least 2 technologies as defined under the technology dimension in the taxonomy.
8. **Barriers/enablers:** Case studies must reflect the diverse categories of barriers/enablers as defined in D2.2. Those having regulatory barrier under the institutional category are not to be considered because of the limited ability to tackle these barriers by improved or novel business models. For the case studies, it must be possible to analyse which type of the barriers/enablers, as defined in D2.2, are important. The identification of barriers and enablers is necessary to interpret the case study results.
9. **KPIs:** A case study must reflect the different categories of KPIs as defined in D2.2. It must be possible to identify which KPIs are operational and determine to which categories of KPIs, as defined in D2.2, they belong.
10. **Transferability:** Case study must be scalable or replicable to other regions/type of infrastructure/modes of transport. Given the relative subjectivity of the assessment at this stage of the project in which critical market information needed to determine transferability parameters is not yet available, this criterion is strongly conditioned to the positive assessment of all prior ones.

Some of these criteria have been used in Proskawetz et al. (2013) for selecting key C-ITS innovations in the smart cities stakeholder platform, whose aim is to accelerate the development and market deployment of energy efficiency and low-carbon technology applications in the urban environment.

5.2 Content validation

A wide range of methods have been employed for validation purposes in case study research; from content, criterion-related to construct validity to mention a few (Brown, 1996). For the purpose of this deliverable, the validation of case studies takes a content validity approach. As the name implies, content validity is the degree to which the content of a case (by definition) is relevant to and representative of the objectives/specifications (validation criteria) for the purpose of meeting the needs of NEWBITS (Brown, 1996, Haynes et al., 1995). In using content validation, the objective is to evaluate the case studies based on the data collected in order to ensure the alignment of their content with the project's requirements, and to ascertain the overall quality of the information obtained. The main goal is to ensure that the validated case studies fit the needs of the project. For determining the validity of the case studies, their contents were assessed against the validation criteria already spelt out in the preceding section.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

The validation assessment was conducted primarily by the WPs 3, 4 and 5 leaders prior to and at the 3rd PMB meeting in Thessaloniki, in consultation with the other partners in the consortium to determine how they fit into the objectives of NEWBITS. Using the content validity approach, it is assumed that the definition contains a detailed description of the case, which is not always true (Trochim, 2000). The validation team requests additional information from the case study leaders for further evaluation whenever necessary, with the possibility to consider alternative case studies if the validation criteria are not met.

The result of the content validation is an evaluation report of the data collected according to the taxonomy fiche and the definitions in Section 4 against the validation criteria, which are detailed in the following subsections. For each criterion, an evaluation score is awarded as follows:

- **2** – The case study fully meets the criterion.
- **1** – The case study partially meets the criterion with limitations.
- **0** – The case study does not meet the criterion.

Based on the validation criteria, a checklist (Table 3) was developed to aid the validation process in examining the content of each case.

Criteria		WPs	Task	Check
Data accessibility	The most critical; stakeholders should be willing to give information needed.	WP3, WP4	All	
Engagement/willingness of stakeholders	Are the stakeholders willing to participate in the case study?	WP4		
Cost-benefit analysis	Can the stakeholders provide sensitive information about cost structure?	WP3, WP4, WP5	Market analysis and stakeholder analysis	
Cost-benefit analysis	Can the stakeholders provide sensitive information about revenue model?	WP3, WP4, WP5	Market analysis and stakeholder analysis	
End-user involvement	Are end-users listed as one of the main stakeholders?	WP3	Conjoint analysis	
Technology	Does the case study cover at least 2-3 technologies (as defined under the technology dimension)? Please state	WP3		
Market segmentation	Does the case study cover at least 2 market segments? Please state.	WP2, WP3		
Market viability	Is the case study public-based/funded and contain market viability information/pre-assessment of the market potential?	WP3, WP4		

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Criteria		WPs	Task	Check
Barriers/Enablers	Are the barriers and enablers known?	WP2		
KPIs	Are the KPIs clearly defined?	WP2		
Transferability	Is the case study scalable or replicable to other regions/type of infrastructure/modes of transport?			

Table 3: Validation criteria checklist

For every case study assessed, the overall validity score is calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{Total evaluation score}}{2 * \text{Number of criteria}} * 10$$

The resulting score determines the level of validity based on the following bands:

- High content validity (8.0 – 10.0)
- Acceptable content validity (5.0 – 7.9)
- Low content validity (0.0 – 4.9)

Case studies adjudged to be of low content validity are discarded from further consideration.

5.2.1 Case study 1 validation

Table 4 summarises the key evidences collected from the taxonomy and definition of CS1 based on the validation criteria checklist.

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
Stakeholder network	The case study has a wide pool of stakeholders comprising 5 groups identified in the taxonomy (government, public authorities, universities/research institutes, industry, end-users). However, most of the main stakeholders such as government, regulatory body, transport operator, road operator, and transport authority are yet to be confirmed. They are considered critical for the analysis of the case study.	1
Data accessibility	Due to the unconfirmed stakeholders within the network, this will directly have repercussions on the access to data in the short term for the execution of WPs 3 and 4. Public authorities may not be willing to share information, and some freight transport companies' handlers may not be knowledgeable enough to provide sensitive information.	0
Innovation level	As one of the critical criteria in the checklist, the case study is currently a new initiative at TRL=1 that is yet to be piloted. Though it has been deployed in the aeronautical domain where there exists an overall governing body (EUROCONTROL), the replication to road transport would require new regulation and standards that could become one of the biggest challenges for deployment, considering the different levels of authorities involved.	0

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
Status	The case study represents a new initiative/research idea that is yet to be transformed into an empirical case. Therefore, it does not fit the definition of case study, nor supports the implementation of NEWBITS methodology.	0
End-user involvement (Conjoint analysis)	Businesses as end-users may not be able to generate the critical mass to support the critical evaluation of end users' preferences according to the methodology to be proposed by the Conjoint analysis. This statistical methodological market research requires a priori a large pool of end users to respond to questionnaires, averaging in some cases to 600 users, though dependent on the number of attributes/preferences considered.	1
Barrier/enabler	The service requires drastic changes in the legal/regulatory framework of freight transport services and a possible infrastructural development before it can be deployed. This institutional barrier can hardly be met within the timeframe of the project, making the possibility of developing a business model unsustainable.	0
Technology	The case study covers all the characteristics of the technology dimension.	2
Market segmentation	The case study offers a wider spectrum of the market segments; ATIS, ATMS, and ATPS.	2
Market viability	So far, there is no assessment on the market potential of the ITS services offered by the case study. Although the initiative is being proposed by an academic stakeholder, it is left to be seen how this can be transferred to the market.	0
KPIs	The two categories of KPIs defined in D2.2 are well covered by the case study.	2
Transferability	The case study has great potential for scalability and replicability to other regions. Also, it is not limited to a particular mode of transport.	2
Validity score		4.54

Table 4: CS1 validation report and score

CS1 reflects the diverse categories in ITS market segments, the different barriers/enablers and KPIs as defined in D2.1 and D2.2 respectively, and also, possesses a great potential for transferability. However, it fails to meet some of the basic parameters required for the deployment of the methodological framework such as the stakeholder management network, market viability, end-user involvement, the innovation level, and data accessibility. The value proposition seems attractive in terms of the integrated cloud-service information sharing system to deal with the tactical demand/capacity balance of freight transport, but more work needs to be done to reach a pilot stage.

5.2.2 Case study 2 validation

Table 5 summarises the key evidences collected from the taxonomy and definition of CS2 based on the validation criteria checklist.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
Stakeholder network	<p>The case study involves stakeholders comprising 5 groups identified in the taxonomy: Government (EC); Public Authorities (Municipality of Verona); Other (Transport Operator), Industry (ITS provider: Telecom Italia; Automotive supplier: AUDI; OEMs: SWARCO), end users (citizens).</p> <p>The network of actors is operative, having been involved in a joint project publicly co-funded by the European Commission CIP Programme, and further developed under a public-private partnership at the end of the project. The relations with transport companies involved in the pilot (ATV, Taxi company, etc.) were maintained primarily through Verona Municipality. Swarco Mizar was the point of contact for all technical issues related to Verona Pilot and providing updated status information about the overall project to the City and additional Transport Companies. Both core stakeholders are part of the case study leader trusted relational network.</p> <p>The case is considered to enable a stakeholder network, being those already effectively confirmed to be engaged in NEWBITS procedure.</p>	2
Data accessibility	<p>Consultation of CS leader with core stakeholders has confirmed the willingness of those to provide access to relevant data. The case is based on a public co-funded project, being most generic information already publicly available at costs, impacts, timing, market viability, barriers-enablers levels.</p> <p>One of the stakeholders is involved in NEWBITS' Stakeholders Advisory Board (SWARCO Mizar), having been timely informed of the project aims, and needs. The links of the case study leader with the municipality (key enabler of the pilot) are robust, based on multiple partnerships.</p> <p>No major contingencies are expected in terms of potentially commercial sensitive information at the level required to deploy WP3 and WP4. NEWBITS consortium will follow the approach defined in the Project Data Management Plan (Section 4.4.1: Other Ethics Requirement) on this particular.</p>	2
Innovation level	<p>The project innovation lies on the introduction of a battery of new services in the city of Verona (such as: Road Hazard Warning, Road Works Warning; Speed advisory based on GLOSA system, Red light violation warning, Transit speed improving through signal priority). The project exhibits a close-to-market innovation (TRL7-8). The tested solutions (services) are defined as "easily to be replicated" by the case study leader.</p>	2
Status	<p>The case study presents a number of embedded services which have been piloted and shown to be accepted. The project Compass4D that supports the case study ended in December 2015. However, the consortium continued operating the ITS services developed without any co-funding, but with the support of ERTICO-ITS Europe.</p> <p>It is considered that the current status of the services piloted in the case to be in the ideal stage to evolve from pilot to deployment site. The need to find the "right" business models is highlighted as critical by the pilot managers.</p>	2

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
End-user involvement (Conjoint analysis)	The CS has potential to engage enough end-users (Verona citizens) to reach the critical mass	1
Barrier/enabler	For the CS, only one type of barrier/enabler is identified.	1
Technology	The CS covers several technologies (short range, long range, camera, road side, personal, vehicle, etc.)	2
Market segmentation	The CS has implemented functionalities covering ATMS, ATIS and CVS.	2
Market viability	The CS services have been already evaluated and accepted by end-users and public authorities have interest implementing them.	2
KPIs	The two categories of KPIs defined in D2.2 are covered by the case study.	2
Transferability	The case study has great potential for scalability and replicability to other regions/cities.	2
Validity score		9.09

Table 5: CS2 validation report and score

CS2 shows a very high relevance to the criteria required in meeting the project's requirements with the exception of the assurance to generate the critical mass of end-users needed for the conjoint analysis in WP3. As such, we can conclude that this case study is highly valid to guarantee the successful deployment of the methodological approach, as the different aspects of the criteria are well covered.

5.2.3 Case study 3 validation

Table 6 summarises the key evidences collected from the taxonomy and definition of CS3 based on the validation criteria checklist. Initially the case study was validated at a score of 9.09 (see table below). However, after a more in-depth discussion with the main stakeholders just after validation process was finalized and reported in a prior version of this deliverable, it appeared that the technology readiness level of the particular case was underestimated. The platform has been implemented and has been further developed already. For the stakeholders, the business modelling of the described case is a crossed bridge and although there was willingness to participate, the case study could not be redefined in a way that was of mutual interest for the stakeholders and the NEWBITS project. This situation affected the scores on stakeholder network, data accessibility, innovation level, status, end-user involvement, and transferability. The initial scores depicted below on the first 5 items have been set to 0 (see

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

final score in table). Transferability was set to a score of 1, as this criterion is not relevant for a case study without support of the stakeholders. The resulting score (4.55) is below 5, leading to dismissal of this case study. An alternative case study 3, also in container transport, has been proposed, defined and validated in 5.4.3.

Criteria	Evaluation	Initial score	Final score
Stakeholder network	<p>Initial score: The case study involves stakeholders in a two-layer level: on the primary level, there are two core partners comprising 2 groups identified in the taxonomy: Academia-University (University of Twente), Industry (at diverse key levels of the supply chain: container terminals, Transport companies' inland waterways and road) and Other (DINALOG, as project management body). At an indirect or secondary level, there are other Industry partners (shippers, skippers and truck drivers), Public Authorities (Port Authorities) and Government (Customs).</p> <p>The network of actors has been involved in a public-private project supported and directed by DINALOG. The initiator of the project was Combi Terminal Twente (CTT). Bolk transport Almelo and Burger Logistics are transport partners in the logistic chain. Inland terminal MCS Meppel is partner to advise on knowledge transfer to other terminals. University Twente delivered ICT knowledge.</p> <p>CS leader counts with strong links with project directing entity (DINALOG). The case is considered to enable a stakeholder network, being those already effectively confirmed to be engaged in NEWBITS procedure.</p> <p>Final score: The stakeholder will not engage in the case study.</p>	2	0
Data accessibility	<p>Initial score: Consultation of CS leader with core stakeholder (DINALOG) has confirmed the willingness of those to provide access to relevant data. More detail is required about the access to specific data related essentially to cost structure and revenue models. The framework defined in the Project Management Plan (Section 4.4.1: Other Ethics Requirement) will be duly implemented if required.</p> <p>One of the stakeholders is involved in NEWBITS' Stakeholders Advisory Board (DINALOG), having been timely informed of the project aims, and needs.</p> <p>Final score: The stakeholder will not further engage in the case study and share data.</p>	2	0
Innovation level	<p>Initial score: The project innovation lies on the design and deployment of a web-based service allowing logistic agents to monitor data about handling and transport of goods 24/7. It is an information service enabling actors (logistic agents) to plan, manage and synchronize available capacity in benefit of the logistic process. The project exhibits a close-to-market innovation (TRL8).</p> <p>Final score: The described platform is part of a commercially used platform that has been further developed. The TRL level is 9.</p>	2	0

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Criteria	Evaluation	Initial score	Final score
Status	<p>Initial score: The functionality in which this case study pivots was part of the SIEEG demonstration project that was implemented from 2011 to 2013 in the framework of a program lead by DINALOG. It has been continued in some other sub-projects, essentially fostered by the initiator (Combi Terminal Twente)</p> <p>Final score: The project has been developed further and the described case is somewhat out-dated.</p>	2	0
End-user involvement (Conjoint analysis)	<p>Initial score: The CS probably will not be able to involve enough end-users to reach the critical mass. There is chance of trying to involve some stakeholders from the last mile which will help a lot with this. In case these stakeholders cannot be involved, the commitment of the current CS stakeholders can help gathering data of the users' preferences.</p> <p>Final score: The CS will not involve end-users</p>	1	0
Barrier/enabler	For the CS, barriers and enablers have been identified covering different categories described in D2.2.	2	2
Technology	The CS uses different technologies: long range, short range, GPS, OCR, algorithms, etc.	2	2
Market segmentation	The CS covers 3 segments, ATIS, ATMS and APTS.	2	2
Market viability	The CS has been already deployed and other inland terminal is already interested in its functionalities	1	1
KPIs	The two categories of KPIs defined in D2.2 are covered by the case study.	2	2
Transferability	<p>Initial score: The new ICT based method to increase efficiency in the total logistics chain of main ports has raised interest of other inland terminals in the EU. It is considered that the case study presents a high potential of transferability. Based on the data provided by the CS leader, it is considered a feasible functionality to be tailored and replicated.</p> <p>Final score: Transferability is not relevant for a case study without support of the stakeholders.</p>	2	1
Validity score		9.09	4.55

Table 6: CS3 validation report and score

The platform described has been implemented and has been further developed already than initially assumed. For the stakeholders, the business modelling of the described case is a crossed bridge and the case study could not be redefined in a satisfying way for both the stakeholders and the NEWBITS project. There was no support to continue the case study as described.

5.2.4 Case study 4 validation

Table 7 summarises the key evidences collected from the taxonomy and definition of CS4 based on the validation criteria checklist.

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
Stakeholder network	<p>The case study involves stakeholders comprising 4 groups identified in the taxonomy: Government (UK Railway Safety and Standards Board); Academia (Coventry University); Industry (Train Manufacturer: Alstom Transport; Train owners: Network Rail; Train Operator: Virgin Trains); Other (Railway regulatory bodies: UK Office of Rail Regulatory); End Users (citizens, indirect actors but ultimately beneficiaries from an increased safety).</p> <p>The network of actors is clearly defined, with strong and very relevant actors operating in UK but with a global scope.</p> <p>The initial project was funded by the EC, with the pilot being partially funded by the Railway Safety and Standards Board (public funding). The current practical implementation is under the auspices of Network Rail (private funding). NEWBITS partner Coventry University acts as leader for the data analysis section of the pilot.</p> <p>The network is operative to date, being involved in an-going project in which the case study is based. The stakeholders thus interact on a regular basis to exchange: technical knowledge, financial information and support, information on data collected, testing and validation of results and discuss on the outcomes of the project. It is considered this to be a clear example of potential value network to be maximized by NEWBITS.</p>	2
Data accessibility	<p>A very positive point to ensure data accessibility lies on the fact that a NEWBITS partner (Coventry University) is leading the on-going data analysis which underpins this case. In depth consultation with the Case study leader shows that most required data shall be available. The framework defined in the Project Management Plan (Section 4.4.1: Other Ethics Requirement) will be duly implemented if required.</p> <p>Another key stakeholder is involved in NEWBITS' Stakeholders Advisory Board (RSSB), having been timely informed of the project aims, and needs. The only difficulty identified at this point regards the availability of data related to specific costs (aligned with CBA in WP5) of Network Rail.</p>	1
Innovation level	<p>Despite being a pilot study, the project exhibits a close-to-market innovation. The solution can be replicated and is currently being applied by a consortium of all key players across the British railway industry under the auspices of Network Rail. It is assessed to be at TRL7.</p>	1
Status	<p>On-going project. The main outcome being a method (intangible), though its application requires tangible assets and results (merely, information to aid decision making).</p>	2
End-user involvement (Conjoint analysis)	<p>Given the CS nature, it is going to be really hard to reach enough end-users to reach the critical mass. Ultimately, some of the CS stakeholders could help reaching end-users in order to gather data about the users' preferences.</p>	1

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
Barrier/enabler	For the CS, barriers and enablers have been identified covering different categories described in D2.2.	2
Technology	The CS cover several technologies: long range, short range, GPS, camera, several sensors (measuring speed, vertical force, longitudinal acceleration, height, etc.), data process, algorithms.	2
Market segmentation	The CS covers mainly ATMS and CVS. It could be considered that one of the modules covers ATIS, since it provides information about the routes and times of the trains to end-users.	2
Market viability	There is a clear need in the UK for solutions aiming at predictive maintenance and improved safety. Since the alternative currently in place is not enough to satisfy the performance KPIs, there is a big market potential for the CS solution.	2
KPIs	The two categories of KPIs defined in D2.2 are covered by the case study.	2
Transferability	The approach based in this case is business to business, with the ultimate aim of benefiting both business and consumers. It is clear how the case could be transferred from the current local (London North-West section) UK based environment towards an EU scale, given the need in the railway industry for initiatives supporting both predictive maintenance and improved safety.	1
Validity score		8.18

Table 7: CS4 validation report and score

Just like CS2 and CS3, the same can be said of the relevance of CS4 in meeting the needs of the project. The downside in this case like the others is the difficulty in reaching enough end-users for the conjoint analysis. It has been envisaged that this can be overcome with the guaranteed commitment of the stakeholders to help collect data on users' preferences. On the other hand, a strong point of this case is that it is publicly funded by the project initiator; the Railway Safety and Standards Board.

5.3 Alternative case study 1 (University VAOPoint Mobility)

The first round of validation found 3 of the preselected case studies suitable, discarding CS1 due to its failure to sufficiently meet critical validation criteria required for the execution of the tasks in the project, such as innovation level, stakeholder network position, status, data accessibility, market viability, and the existence of a strong regulatory barrier. As a result, an alternative case study is necessary to complete the 4-case study approach. This requires repeating the tasks in phases 2 and 3 of the methodology described earlier in Chapter 1. A new case study was proposed by the CS leader (UAB) by maximising their network in the field, knowing the full validation requirements as a result of the first-round evaluation. The previous steps of taxonomy fiche data collection, definition, and validation were repeated for the alternative CS (described in the following sections).

5.3.1 Alternative case study 1 description

The University VAOPoint Mobility case study aims to increase the average occupation and achieving a rational use of cars in a university environment with high levels of daily influx of private vehicles. It offers an intelligent carpooling service for daily mobility to the campus, where members of the university community can access numerous carpooling offers. In addition to traditional cost savings on sharing transportation expenses, VAOPoint promotes the reduction of users' carbon footprint and decrease traffic congestion by promoting high-occupancy vehicles.

VAOPoint has already been piloted at the UAB (Figure 7) whose mobility plan includes promoting collective transport, journeys by bicycles as well as achieving more rational use of private vehicles matching the goals of VAOPoint. UAB campus get filled up with over 13,000 vehicles of a very low occupation index: 1.2 people per vehicle - the same average as that of the metropolitan region of Barcelona.

The case study objectives rely mainly on three aspects:

- Efficiency: Matching users to vehicles that minimize trajectory deviations and maximize economic efficiency.
- Comfort: Encourage social preferences matching, avoid campus pathway bottlenecks and guarantee parking availability.
- Environmental issues: Reduce the carbon footprint (CO₂) and pollution as a result of the reduction in the number of cars used.

These objectives have been validated at the UAB with a measurable impact of an increase in car occupancy factor. This in consequence has reduced the number of vehicles accessing the campus facilities through different control systems, in which a real-time information sharing mechanism is critical for the robustness and resilience of the ITS service. The analysis of this case study will include lessons learnt from the pilot. The application of NEWBITS business modelling methodology is expected to pave the way for maximizing the high potential of the case study for transferability to other markets such as intercity solutions involving city councils and industrial district mobility.

L'ORDRE DELS FACTORS
SÍ ALTERA EL PRODUCTE

No és el mateix

4

Que

1

PARTICIPA AL SERVEI DE
COTXE COMPARTIT

 VAOPOINT

PER LA SETMANA DE
LA MOBILITAT I
PARTICIPA EN EL
SORTEIG D'UN
SAMSUNG
GALAXY S7

© NEWBITS

 UAB
Universitat Autònoma
de Barcelona

Mes informació:
<http://VAOpoint-uab.aslogic.es>
<http://www.uab.cat/accessibilitat-transport>

Figure 7: UAB pilot marketing campaign

5.3.2 Alternative case study 1 definition

The VAOPoint case study is defined as follows according to the dimensions of the taxonomy (see taxonomy fiche in Appendix 2.5):

Description: After a failed attempt to recover administrative support from two municipalities in the Barcelona province in deploying a sustainable intercity mobility solution, VAOPoint offers a second level carpooling service for access to university campuses. The project initiated by an SME (a university spin-off company) has been piloted in its first city trial/deployment to members of the university community for access to the campus. Its primary objective is to reduce the number of cars accessing the campus, which in turn reduces users' carbon footprint (CO₂) and pollution. Other secondary aims include the provision of comfort to users and efficiency, by minimising as much as possible trajectory deviations and everyday bottlenecks in campus facilities, guaranteeing access to parking area, and encouraging social preference matching of users.

The project proposes a differential innovation, since it introduces a new service in an existing market that can reduce the flow of vehicles into the university campus, but also can be applied to other transit scenarios with similar problems outside of the University such as interurban mobility and industrial parks.

ACS1 is composed of nine stakeholders ranging from ITS service provider, ITS association, University, mobility department acting as transport authority, to social media marketing agency. It has been funded by an EC project whose aims are to promote the use of FIWARE technologies (through the awarded projects) and the uptake of developed mobility applications as well as to support SMEs and start-ups to develop Smart Mobility applications for cities across Europe. The main end-users are members of the University community; students and University employees. Some potential stakeholders have been identified in ICT service providers and municipalities.

Scope: ACS1 focus is on road transport with a target geographic coverage of urban and motorway. Only personal vehicles are considered. It serves four purposes:

- Traffic management: Supports tactical demand capacity balance.
- Parking: Provides real time information about available free parking areas for high-occupancy vehicles.
- Public transport: Provides new public transport services for intra-campus mobility.
- Environmental protection: Reduces the amount of CO₂ impact and fuel burning.

Technology: The service offered employs both short-range (WiFi) and long range (4G) as enabling ITS communication technology. It relies mainly on smart soft-sensors, for matching, tracking and identification purposes, however some cameras are optionally used at parking areas for validation purposes. The hardware technologies include a university centralised mobility management system, personal mobile phones required for tracking purpose, and cameras at parking areas. Algorithms and simulation are used to compute the demand-capacity matching, and to predict the effects of public transport services for intra-campus mobility, respectively.

Business model: The value proposition is an intangible web service system to fulfil the mobility demands of drivers and passengers. The infrastructure facilities are owned by the university management body which governs the network as a public institution. The network could be transferred also to a public-private maintenance and exploitation at future steps. Stakeholders have different objectives and varying degree of needs, with knowledge, policy and monetary representing the main value flows between them.

The target market segments include ATIS, ATPS, and APTS, while the commerce strategy is of two types; B2B and B2C. Impact is generally positive showing a reduction in the number of vehicles on campus as a result of high-occupancy. This impact has direct consequences economic wise on fuel reduction, and environmentally on emission reductions. Some important KPIs are: % change in level of emissions, % change in the number of vehicles on campus, average occupancy level, number of visits to website of the ITS service, and % change in average journey time. The timing of the project is generally short term for deployment.

On market viability, the European strategy on urban environment recognises the need to encourage the use of sustainable transport modes by favouring public transport over private so as to reduce the use of private vehicles in daily trips to and from European universities. The main barriers to market entry include lack of user acceptance, lack of cooperation between stakeholders, readiness of the infrastructure, and in some cases, technical barrier involving high occupancy vehicle identification and lack of political prioritisation for extension to other markets. The principal enabler for the university market is institutional because universities want to preserve green areas and other facilities and avoid investing in new parking or pathways. Other drivers are; economic (reduced cost from highly-occupied vehicles), technical (an open standard technology architecture, FIWARE), and proven benefits that will permit the transferability to other markets using the university version of the service as a platform to increase its credibility in future dealings with City Councils.

5.3.3 Alternative case study 1 validation

Table 8 summarises the key evidences collected from the taxonomy of ACS1 based on the validation criteria checklist.

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
Stakeholder network	<p>The case study involves stakeholders comprising 6 groups identified in the taxonomy: Government (European Commission); Public Authorities (University governing body; University/Municipal transport authority); Academia (UAB); Industry (ITS service provider: Aslogic; Social media marketing: Websays); Other (Spanish University Association, CRUE); End users (students and university employees).</p> <p>The network of actors is clearly defined, being locally characterized. It is stated that the case has the potential to reach other potential</p>	2

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<p>stakeholders such as: Industry (ICT service providers: Tracking and Communication i.e. Fleet Mobile, Tom-tom) and other Public administrations (city councils of Barcelona and Sabadell already expressed interest).</p> <p>The initiator of the project is the ITS service provider: Aslogic. Aslogic is also a member of the project Stakeholders Advisory Board (SAB). NEWBITS partner and Case study leader UAB has been directly involved in the pilot design and implementation both at technical and management levels. The pilot was embedded into a higher-level initiative fostered by the Association of Universities in Spain, which fostered the development of similar applications. Thus, it can be stated that the case presents a clear value network at local level (which potentially can be expanded from University towards Barcelona city level) and a potential value network at Spain national level through CRUE.</p> <p>The network is operative to date, based on the provision of the service piloted.</p>	
Data accessibility	<p>The project was funded under the Frontier-Cities FP7 project, thus some of the information and data is already publicly available.</p> <p>As for ACS1, a very positive point of this alternative case in terms of ensuring data accessibility is the fact that a NEWBITS partner (UAB) is a primary stakeholder. Moreover, the initiator actor (Aslogic) is a spin-off of UAB in which several members of the UAB team are involved as scientific directors and/or co-founders (also a SAB member). Both stakeholders have expressed willingness to grant access to the information as required by the project.</p> <p>The framework defined in the Project Management Plan (Section 4.4.1: Other Ethics Requirement) will be duly implemented if required.</p>	2
Innovation level	<p>It is a pilot project, offering a carpooling ITS based application. The assessment of the state of the art of the pilot results in the consideration of being at TRL7.</p>	2
Status	<p>The first deployment of VAOpoint has been UAB campus in Bellaterra, Barcelona. The project is currently being finalized towards a full carpooling solution with geo-localization. It is considered to be in an appropriate status for allowing NEWBITS process to be deployed, as well as to maximize the expected impacts of it.</p>	2
End-user involvement (Conjoint analysis)	<p>The CS has big potential of reaching end-users. With 2.000 persons in the administrative staff and 40.000 students only in the Barcelona University.</p>	2
Barrier/enabler	<p>For the CS, barriers and enablers have been identified covering different categories described in D2.2.</p>	2
Technology	<p>The CS includes several technologies: long range, short range, sensors, cameras, smart phones, GPS.</p>	2

Market segmentation	The CS covers in one or other aspects, all the market segments, mainly ATIS, APTS and ATPS.	2
Market viability	The CS has big market potential. All the areas covered in the CS are strong trends in mobility, the market is growing and there is a big demand for this type of services.	2
KPIs	The two categories of KPIs defined in D2.2 are covered by the case study.	2
Transferability	The case study presents high transferability potential. This is due to several facts: i) It has been designed and piloted in and for a very specific environment (a university campus) and following a Spanish wide experience. The resulting service could be easily extrapolated to a number of university campuses world-wide; ii) The technology mix has been designed and implemented in order to allow an extrapolation towards an urban environment. This is related to the fact that originally the scope of the project pilot was meant to be Barcelona/Sabadell cities, changing last-minute due to political agenda changes; iii) The service is applicable to other transit scenarios with similar problems, such as industrial parks.	2
Validity score		10

Table 8: ACS1 validation report and score

Unlike the previously preselected case studies, ACS1 represents a perfect match in its content to the project's requirements. It stands out with the high potential to reach a large number of end-users for the conjoint analysis to be implemented in D3.2 and gathering sufficient information on users' preferences. Another positive aspect is the high potential of transferring the services to different markets such as other university campuses within and out of Spain, cities, interurban, and particularly industrial parks since one of its reward model is based on parking management.

5.4 Alternative case study 3 (Synchro modal transport corridor Rotterdam- Limburg)

The first round of validation found 3 of the preselected case studies suitable, discarding CS1. At a later stadium, also Case study 3 was discarded. As a result, an alternative case study 3 is necessary to complete the 4-case study approach. This requires repeating the tasks in phases 2 and 3 of the methodology described earlier in Chapter 1. A new case study was proposed by the CS leader (CED) with aid of TKI Dinalog, knowing the full validation requirements as a result of the first-round evaluation. The previous steps of taxonomy fiche data collection, definition, and validation were repeated for the alternative CS (described in the following sections).

5.4.1 Alternative case study 3 description

The use case "synchromodal container transport corridor Rotterdam-Limburg" has been initiated by three parties involved in the supply chain of container shipment together with project leader TNO. Synchro modality refers to the possibility of choosing the most optimal transport modality at the moment of transshipment (or the possibility of transshipment). To allow this, real time information is needed on the transport chain. In the pilot project a platform is being developed to share real time data on container transport from deep sea terminal

Rotterdam to warehouses in Limburg (NL). The data collecting involves tracking of the sea ships heading for Rotterdam, container handling in the port of Rotterdam, inland ship and truck transport and handling of the containers at the inland terminal.

In a previous phase to the current pilot project, a demonstrator has been developed, showing that it is technically possible to integrate various data streams and show the real-time location of containers. The current project stage is focused on i) including more shippers, ii) including data from the sea terminals and new inland waterway terminal, and iii) finalizing an operational IT platform. In this sense, additional stakeholders have been involved, including ICT and ITS companies that have experience in real time mapping and software development.

The features developed in the service are the following:

- Real time location of containers
- ETA and ATA³ at the various moments in the supply chain

In the previous demonstration phase, it appeared that containers in the hinterland transport spend quite some time (ca. 2/3) at containers stacks at the terminals, without awareness of the logistic planners. With the developed service, real-time container information will become available to the logistic planner and travel time can be reduced. In addition, better planning in advance can reduce last minute truck transport and more containers can be transported by inland waterway transport and reduced GHG emissions. Besides time reduction and modal shift, the real-time information is expected to lead to better use of barge capacity, less communication on the planning, and better use of resources.

5.4.2 Alternative case study 3 definition

Description: The case study is on a pilot study called “synchromodal container transport corridor Rotterdam-Limburg”. The project under study aims at proofing the benefits of real time information on container transport. In the pilot project an already developed and tested research platform is further developed and converted to an operational platform that finally should be exploited by a commercial party.

The main objective of the project is to give good insight in the status of containers from sea to warehouses in the hinterland. This allows:

- To optimally plan resources and work teams
- to reduce slack in the planning; often containers remain on the terminals longer than necessary due to lack of information.
- to support synchro modal transport and increase the share of inland waterway transport due to improved planning possibilities.
- Reduction of ad-hoc communication

The project proposes a differential type of innovation. The container transport efficiency on an existing link is improved. The innovation of the project is provision of real time data on container

³ ETA = Estimated time of arrival, ATA = Actual time of arrival

transport on the complete chain from sea to hinterland. It includes the information of sea ships, deep sea terminals, inland waterway vessels, trucks and inland terminals.

The project is led by research institute TNO and is supported by TKI Dinalog, an institute based on public-private partnership that aims to boost innovation in logistics in the Netherlands. The service is piloted for the logistic planning of a shipper, its warehouse operator and an inland container terminal. The project involves several other stakeholders: ITS and ICT service providers, the deep sea port authority, a port data supplier and a regional development company.

Scope: The project is on intermodal transport (road and inland waterways, potentially also rail) on the link Rotterdam- Limburg. It serves the following purposes:

- Increased transparency and efficiency of container transport from deep sea terminals to the hinterland
- Reduction of transport time from 10 days to 3 days (ambition)
- Better planning of resources/ work teams
- Increase the attractiveness of inland waterway transport

Technology: The developed ICT platform combines data from Sea ships, sea port, hinterland traffic and inland ports. The following communication is active:

- Ships (sea and inland waterways) are followed by AIS
- Trucks are followed with GPS
- Container handling data from the deep-sea terminal are shared with the system
- Container handling data at the inland terminal are shared with the system

The system provides information that can be used by shipper and logistic service providers in the chain. It also contains algorithms to estimate time of arrival based on actual traffic information and statistics. The system does not yet contain active decision support; however, it allows for better decision making.

Business Model: The value proposition is an intangible web service system that collects information on container transport from stakeholders in the transport chain. The objectives and needs of stakeholders differ. Platform design and logistic data are the main value flows between stakeholders.

The service includes elements of ATIS (Real time information is used to inform operators in the logistics chain to allow them to synchronize their activities) and ATMS (logistic planners receive real time information to improve their planning and optimize e.g. the use of inland shipping), while the commerce strategy is B2B. The main impacts expected are reduction in delays on the transport leg Rotterdam- Limburg, efficient use of resources and work teams and a higher share of inland waterway transport.

The ICT partners are interested in commercializing the platform developed. Also, other inland terminals are interested in this functionality.

The main barrier of the service is the access to real-time data from the seaport, more specifically the data on handling at the deep-sea terminals. Both data sensitivity and technical

issues hamper the data availability. Enablers identified are the development of API's with good data governance and the economic benefits the system can offer.

5.4.3 Alternative case study 3 validation

Table 9 summarises the key evidences collected from the taxonomy of CS3 based on the validation criteria checklist.

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
Stakeholder network	<p>The logistic chain serviced consists of a shipper, an inland terminal and a warehouse operator. ITS and ICT companies are involved to deliver ITS/ ICT knowledge, data and the frontend of the platform. Other stakeholders are the deep-sea port authority, a regional network organisation for medium and small enterprises.</p> <p>The case study is based on a demonstration project lead by research institute TNO. The project is supported and funded by TKI Dinalog</p> <p>CS leader counts with strong links with both the project leader of the pilot study (TNO) and the project directing entity (DINALOG). All stakeholder have been contacted by TNO to confirm engagement in the NEWBITS procedure.</p>	2
Data accessibility	<p>Consultation of CS leader with the project leader of the pilot study has confirmed the willingness of the stakeholders to provide access to relevant data. It has been agreed with the stakeholders that the NEWBITS case study leader will sign a confidentiality agreement to give the possibility to share confidential information if needed. Some stakeholder will be treated anonymously. The framework defined in the Project Management Plan (Section 4.4.1: Other Ethics Requirement) will be duly implemented if required.</p> <p>The stakeholders involved have been informed of the project aims, and needs. The link of the case study leader with TNO (project leader of pilot study) is robust.</p>	2
Innovation level	<p>The project innovation lies on the design and deployment of platform service allowing logistic agents to monitor data about container handling and transport. It is an information service enabling actors (logistic agents) to plan, manage and synchronize available capacity in benefit of the logistic process. The project is in advanced pilot phase (TRL7).</p>	1
Status	<p>The pilot is planned to be finished in February 2018. At this stage, the pilot project team is actively assessing the business model of the service.</p>	2
End-user involvement (Conjoint analysis)	<p>The CS probably will not be able to involve enough end-users to reach the critical mass. There is chance of trying to involve some (potential) end-users which will help a lot with this. In case these stakeholders cannot be involved, the commitment of the current CS stakeholders can help gathering data of the users' preferences.</p>	1
Barrier/enabler	<p>For the CS, barriers and enablers have been identified covering different categories described in D2.2.</p>	2

Criteria	Evaluation	Evaluation score
Technology	The CS uses different technologies: AIS (long range and short range), GPS, API algorithms, etc.	2
Market segmentation	The CS covers 2 segments: ATIS, ATMS.	2
Market viability	The CS has been already deployed and other inland terminal is already interested in its functionalities	1
KPIs	The two categories of KPIs defined in D2.2 are covered by the case study.	2
Transferability	The new ICT based method to increase efficiency in the total logistics chain. The service can be transferred to other links between Rotterdam and the hinterland. There are about 30 inland terminals in the Netherlands. It even has the potential to be used for rail terminals or other deeps sea terminals.	2
Validity score		8.64

Table 9: ACS1 validation report and score

ACS3 represents a perfect match in its content to the project's requirements. The contact with the stakeholders and the information gathering has been effectively arranged. Another positive aspect is the pilot study stakeholder group is in a process of assessing the business model of their service.

5.5 Gender analysis of validated case studies

This section focuses on identifying any possible gaps in gender relations and roles in the context of the validated case studies. As already elaborated in D1.1, the gender analysis plan in NEWBITS follows a checklist approach in which a set of gender-focused questions is introduced in a number of WPs tasks to determine the consideration of gender dimension. The questions specifically oriented to this deliverable as defined in D1.1 are given as follows:

- a. How catalytic are the case studies in advancing women's well-being, empowerment and gender equality?
- b. Having framed the application areas of the case studies, do the contexts suggest different patterns of use by different groups of potential consumers (men-women)?

5.5.1 CS1 gender dimension

In CS1, all users' needs and expectations both men and women, are taken into account equally during the development of the platform. It is accessible to both genders. The platform does not differentiate drivers or passengers by gender in any way. In the pilot, users share the same mobility needs and purpose (work/study) with a common origin and/or destination; travel to/from the university. Since the sexes of users are not revealed during the pilot, they are not

known differences in sex and inequality in the usage patterns (no discriminatory usage pattern). There are neither gaps nor disparities in participation rates and access to the service by men and women.

5.5.2 CS2 gender dimension

CS2 does not distinguish stakeholders by a gender-related point of view, nor distinguished any kind of group, or segment, or cluster of users. Any kind of information about involved users that can be capable of depict socio-economic and personal characteristics of the users itself, is thus not available. As a result, it is not possible to determine the capacity of the project to accelerate the advancing of women's well-being, empowerment and gender equality.

5.5.3 CS3 gender dimension

The case study Synchronodal transport on corridor Rotterdam-Limburg focuses on efficient hinterland transport of containers. It concerns a business-to-business (B2B) service with logistic planners being the customers. Having no private persons as customers, there is no direct influence on women's well-being, empowerment and gender equality. There might be indirect influences, through the characteristics of businesses profiting from the case study outcomes; however, such influences are unknown.

5.5.4 CS4 gender dimension

This case study does not distinguish its stakeholders from a gender-related point of view. As all organisations within the railway industry and the railway passengers, staff and communities, there is no distinction of any kind of group, segment or cluster of users. All data collected is about either infrastructure or statistical (e.g. station foothold), so no socio-economic, or personal identifiable information is collected or treated as part of the case study. Thus, it is difficult to argue that the case study has the potential to impact women's well-being, empowerment or gender equality.

6. Conclusion

As the main enabler of the methodological framework of NEWBITS, case studies are considered more appropriate to gain deeper understanding of the changing conditions affecting the deployment of ITS innovations. They will ensure the feasible parameterisation of the business ecosystem concept and allow the implementation of the business modelling approach to be deployed in this project, besides the fact that they are able to provide solid evidences beyond extrapolations.

Following the results of Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2, the next step is to validate the preselected case studies and create the taxonomy of those. Although 4 case studies have been selected at the proposal stage based on a set of pre-established criteria, it was agreed at the consortium level that they are not sufficient to determine the relevance of the case studies in meeting the project's needs. This is because a validation process was not in place a priori, and also, due to the fact that the case studies have been mimicked at the proposal stage.

Owed to the need to gather detailed information for these case studies in the validation process, a structured methodological approach has been deployed such that the entire process is carried out in a reverse logical step using a 3-phase methodology.

The first phase dealing with the taxonomy development reveals that a comprehensive taxonomy is needed beyond the categorisations defined in D21.1 and D2.2, scope, ITS application area, technology, and problem addressed. Due to the importance of business models in the NEWBITS project, the requirements of WPs 3, 4 and 5 were addressed by taking into account the inputs from the WP leaders as well the synthesis of the literature on business models. The development process resulted in 4 taxonomy dimensions (*Description*, *Scope*, *Technology*, and *Business model*) building on the previous works on taxonomy of Smart City and City Logistics projects, in addition to the previously limited dimensions defined in D2.1. Apart from its capability to translate the characteristics of ITS services into a structured classification scheme, the taxonomic framework has been developed in this deliverable to serve two purposes: As a data collection framework to define the case studies (Phase 2) and as a validation base for evaluating the case studies (Phase 3).

Given the taxonomy developed in the first phase, the second phase then went further to thoroughly define the case studies by gathering information from a variety of sources using the taxonomy fiche. Each case study is defined according to the 4 dimensions of the taxonomy, which serves as input to the next phase. The third phase deploys the validation process to determine whether the case studies fulfil the requirements of the business ecosystem approach and in particular, WPs 3, 4 and 5. Also, the overall quality of the information obtained is evaluated given the taxonomy framework for the identification of the data available.

In the first stage of the validation phase, only three cases were deemed suitable from the validation criteria evaluation. The preselected CS1 was discarded based on its failure to meet 5 of the critical validation requirements that are essential to perform subsequent tasks in market analysis and business model development. One being on the basis of the status; CS1 is still at the conception stage which is more like a theoretical concept that is yet to develop into an empirical case. Other criteria that hindered its usefulness are stakeholder network position, data accessibility, market viability, and regulatory barrier.

The outcome of the first stage calls for the need to propose an alternative case study. Another round of validation was then initiated. Knowing the full validation requirements as a result of the first-round evaluation, CS1 leader (UAB) was charged with the task to come up with a new case study by maximising their network in the field. The VAOPoint CS was proposed as an alternative in which the previous steps of taxonomy fiche data collection, definition, and validation were repeated. It stood out with the critical mass of end-users involvement for the conjoint analysis to be implemented in D3.2. Other criteria were also strongly assessed to ensure its validity in achieving NEWBITS objectives. The whole validation results show that the different aspects of the tasks to be executed in subsequent WPs have been thoroughly covered.

In a later stage of the deliverable, right after it was edited and submitted in its version 1.0, the pre-selected CS3 was also discarded due new information arriving from the main stakeholder involved in the case, which affected critically the possibility to establish a stakeholders network and the possibility to access reliable data to perform NEWBITS approach. CS3 leader (CED), in close cooperation with PC (ORT), WP3 leader (ATOS) and D2.3 leader (UAB), was charged to browse for an alternative case. All consortium partners coupled this browsing effort in order to ensure a feasible case in a short timing. CED proposed the alternative case 3 which was assessed against the validation criteria and considered perfectly suited for NEWBITS. The results of this “ex post” procedure have resulted in D2.3 version 1.1., which collates the new information on the basis of prior D2.3 version 1.0.

Overall, the outcome of this deliverable will set the platform to properly execute the linked tasks in other WPs with the case studies validated through a prior established taxonomy and definitions. The case studies have provided a well-balanced picture of the different transport modes (road, water, and rail) and types (personal, public, and freight). For each of the validated case study, a thorough market and conjoint analyses will be performed in WP3, with the subsequent WP4 deploying a network-based business modelling approach in order to provide the key to understanding the competitive environment.

References

- Benjelloun, A., Crainic, T. G., & Bigras, Y. (2010). Towards a taxonomy of City Logistics projects. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(3), 6217-6228.
- Bohm, M. (2016). European ITS Toolkit provides valuable lessons in terms of ITS data availability and comparability. <http://its-observatory.eu/european-its-toolkit-provides-valuable-lessons-in-terms-of-its-data-availability-and-comparability/>
- Böhm, M., Studer, L., & Mans, D. (2010). Toolkit for Sustainable Decision Making In ITS Deployment. In paper at the ITS World Congress, Busan.
- Brown, J. D. (1996). *Testing in language programs*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall Regents
- Cagliano, A. C., Marco, A. D., Mangano, G., & Zenezini, G. (2016). Assessing City Logistics projects: a business-oriented approach.
- Cavaye, A. L. (1996). Case study research: a multi-faceted research approach for IS. *Information systems journal*, 6(3), 227-242.
- C-ITS Platform (2016), Final report, Brussels
- Darke, P., Shanks, G., & Broadbent, M. (1998). Successfully completing case study research: combining rigour, relevance and pragmatism. *Information systems journal*, 8(4), 273-289.
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989). Building theories from case study research. *Academy of management review*, 14(4), 532-550.
- El-Araby, K., Dinkel A., Kulmala R., & Magerl E. (2010). D1.1 – Selection criteria and classification of ITS applications. Toolkit for sustainable decision making in ITS deployment, 2DECIDE, 1-78.
- Ferrero, F., Perboli, G., Vesco, A., Caiati, V., & Gobbato, L. (2015). Car-sharing services—part a taxonomy and annotated review. Submitted to *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*.
- Gershenson, J. K., & Stauffer, L. A. (1999). A taxonomy for design requirements from corporate customers. *Research in Engineering Design*, 11(2), 103-115.
- Gibbs, H., & Chapman-Novakofski, K. (2013). Peer Reviewed: Establishing Content Validity for the Nutrition Literacy Assessment Instrument. *Preventing chronic disease*, 10.
- Gregor, D., Toral, S., Ariza, T., Barrero, F., Gregor, R., Rodas, J., & Arzamendia, M. (2016). A methodology for structured ontology construction applied to intelligent transportation systems. *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, 47, 108-119.
- Haas, P., Blohm, I., & Leimeister, J. M. (2014). An empirical taxonomy of crowdfunding intermediaries.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Haynes, S. N., Richard, D., & Kubany, E. S. (1995). Content validity in psychological assessment: A functional approach to concepts and methods. *Psychological assessment*, 7(3), 238.

ITS Observatory Consortium (2017) <http://its-observatory.eu>, Accessed May 4, 2017.

ITS Toolkit (2017). European ITS Toolkit. www.its-toolkit.eu. Accessed May 5, 2017.

Kadareja, A. (2015). Risks of incremental, differential, radical, and breakthrough innovation projects. www.innovationmanagement.se/2013/07/29.

Kohlbacher, F. (2006, January). The Use of Qualitative Content Analysis in Case Study Research. In *Forum: Qualitative Social Research* (Vol. 7, No. 1).

Kulmala, R., Mans, D., El-Araby, K., & Penttinen, M. (2013). How to infer impacts of ITS services in different user cases. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, 7(3), 275-282.

Labes, S., Ereğ, K., & Zarnekow, R. (2013). Common patterns of cloud business models, in Proceedings of 19th Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS 2013), Chicago, USA.

Lirzin, F., & Schramm, C. (2012). Reindustrialising Europe: the issues at stake in a European Innovation and Industrial Policy. *Foundation Robert Schuman, European Issues*, (256).

Misuraca, G. (2010). Methodology and Guidelines for Case Study Research, Exploring emerging ICT-enabled governance models in European cities (EXPGOV) project

Moore, James F. (1993). Predators and prey, a new ecology of competition. *Harvard Business Review*, May-June 1993.

Müller, K.-P., & Roodt, G. (2013). Content validation: The forgotten step-child or a crucial step in assessment centre validation? *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology/SA Tydskrif vir Bedryfsielkunde*, 39(1), Art. #1153, 15 pages.

Nickerson, R. C., Varshney, U., & Muntermann, J. (2013). A method for taxonomy development and its application in information systems. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 22(3), 336-359.

Österle, H., Becker, J., Frank, U., Hess, T., Karagiannis, D., Krcmar, H., ... & Sinz, E. J. (2011). Memorandum on design-oriented information systems research. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 20(1), 7-10.

Payne, S. (2015). Study on key performance indicators for intelligent transport systems: final report in support of the implementation of the EU Legislative Framework on ITS (Directive 2010/40/EU).

Perboli, G., De Marco, A., Perfetti, F., & Marone, M. (2014). A new taxonomy of smart city projects. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 3, 470-478.

Proskawetz, K., Klug S., & Beckert, B. (2013). Key to Innovation Integrated Solution, Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems and Services (C-ITS). *Smart Cities Stakeholder Platform*, 1-23.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Rafiq, G., Talha, B., Patzold, M., Luis, J. G., Ripa, G., Carreras, I., ... & Desaeger, M. (2013). What's new in intelligent transportation systems?: An overview of european projects and initiatives. *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, 8(4), 45-69.

Remane, G., Nickerson, R., Hanelt, A., Tesch, J. F., & Kolbe, L. M. (2016). A Taxonomy of Carsharing Business Models. 37th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2016), Dublin, Ireland.

Ricardo (2016), Study on the Deployment of C-ITS in Europe: Final Report, London

RITA U.S. DoT, U. (2015), Taxonomy of intelligent transportation systems application. <http://www.itslessons.its.dot.gov>.

Stake, R. E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Sage.

Stanton, N. A., & Salmon, P. M. (2009). Human error taxonomies applied to driving: A generic driver error taxonomy and its implications for intelligent transport systems. *Safety Science*, 47(2), 227-237.

SWIM (2017). <http://www.eurocontrol.int/swim>. Accessed July 10, 2017.

Taniguchi, E., Thompson, R. G., & Yamada, T. (2003). Predicting the effects of city logistics schemes. *Transport Reviews*, 23(4), 489-515.

Trace, C. (2001). Applying content analysis to case study data: A preliminary report. *Retrieved May, 27, 2005*.

Trochim, W. (2000). *The Research Methods Knowledge Base*, 2nd Edition. Atomic Dog Publishing, Cincinnati, OH.

TTRANS project (2013). Enhancing transfer of ITS innovations to the market, *Deliverable 3.1-ITS state of the art assessment* [Online], Available at: <http://www.ttransnetwork.eu/ttrans/its-state-of-the-art-assessment/>. Accessed 10th July, 2017

TTRANS project (2013a). Enhancing transfer of ITS innovations to the market, Deliverable 3.2-T-TRANS Roadmap Report [Online], Available at: <http://www.ttransnetwork.eu/ttrans/roadmap-report/>. Accessed 10th July, 2017.

US Department of Transportation, Research and Innovative Technology Administration RITA: 'Intelligent Transport Systems. ITS benefits database'. Available at <http://www.itsbenefits.its.dot.gov/>

Van Rees, R. (2003). Clarity in the usage of the terms ontology, taxonomy and classification. *CIB REPORT*, 284(432), 1-8.

Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods*. In *Applied Social Research Methods Series* (Vol. 5). Sage Publications.

Appendices

Appendix 1 Taxonomy fiche

Case study name		
Description		
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety • Efficiency • Comfort • Environment 	Discuss the objectives of the case study and the problem addressed. Indicate in the description all the primary benefits the case study are aimed at.
Innovation Level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployed • Close-to-market • Emerging • Pilot 	Describe the innovation phase of the case study according to the TRL (assess the maturity of the service)
Innovation Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incremental • Differential • Radical • Breakthrough 	<p>According to the following definitions (Kadareja, 2015), specify the type of innovation according to the degree of novelty and justify how the services offered in the case study match the type:</p> <p>Incremental: Incremental changes to existing products, projects that are typically focused on line changes or improvements in a firm's existing product offerings.</p> <p>Differential: New products for the same markets, moderately innovative products for existing markets.</p> <p>Radical: New products for new markets.</p> <p>Breakthrough: New products that create new markets that usually refer to revolutionary change in firms, markets and industries, which provide substantially higher customer benefits relative to current products in the industry.</p>
Type of Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government • Public authorities • Industry/ITS associations • European Commission • Academia • End users • Others 	Briefly describe the key stakeholders that are involved in the project (must match the groups listed in the left cell/column). Exact entity/organisation names are highly encouraged if there is no disclosure agreement.
Project Initiator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private • Public • Public-private 	Briefly discuss the sector that launched the case study
Scope		
Transport Mode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unimodal (road, rail, air, water) • Multimodal 	Briefly discuss the transport mode.
Transport Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal • Public • Freight 	Briefly discuss the transport type.
Geographic coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban • Motorway • Corridor 	Briefly discuss the geographical scale of the case study; indicate multiple options wherever applicable.
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road safety • Traffic management 	Discuss the purposes of the case study; indicate multiple options wherever applicable.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freight services • Parking • Routing • Vulnerable road user • Public Transport • Environmental Protection • Automotive Telematics • Road user charging • Automated Vehicles 	
Technology		
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short range • Long range • Hybrid 	<p>Discuss briefly the communication channels used in the case study:</p> <p>Short range – WLAN; DSRC (ITS G5), 802.11p WAVE, Wi-Fi suitable for V2V and V2I</p> <p>Long range - Cellular networks/WAN (GPRS(2G), 3G, 4G), suitable for V2I</p> <p>Hybrid – A combination of the above two.</p>
Sensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radar • Camera • Road side beacons 	Discuss briefly the sensing technologies used in the case study
Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central • Roadside • Personal • Vehicle 	<p>Discuss briefly the hardware used in the case study:</p> <p>Central: Centralised traffic management system</p> <p>Roadside: Beacons, poles, smart traffic lights...</p> <p>Personal: Mobile phones, tablets, personal navigation devices, and other hand-held devices.</p> <p>Vehicle: Hardware installed in the vehicle to enable communications (V2V, V2I)</p>
Decision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Algorithms • Simulation 	Discuss briefly the decision technologies (software-based systems) used for the design, analysis, planning, management, and control of the ITS services.
Business Model		
Product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tangible • Intangible 	Briefly discuss the kind of product offered.
Infrastructure financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public • Private • Public-Private 	Discuss the main financing sources/providers of the infrastructure used in the case study.
Operation financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public • Private • Public-Private 	Discuss the sources of operation financing.
Management of network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public • Private • Public-Private 	Briefly discuss how the network is managed. How is the network governed? By a public body, if it is 100% publicly funded. By a major stakeholder that is a private company and dominant on the market, the so called a private dominant leadership. And thirdly, by an equally integrated private-public partnership.
Stakeholder grouping*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role • Objectives 	Role: Brief list of the stakeholders' main activities/role in the network.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Needs Input Output 	<p>Interest/Objectives: Main purpose of the stakeholder. The point or status he is trying to reach.</p> <p>Needs: Things the stakeholder may need to reach his objectives.</p> <p>Inputs: What the stakeholder uses [or could use]/receive from other stakeholders.</p> <p>Outputs: What the stakeholder produces and is [or could be] used by other stakeholders.</p>
Stakeholder interaction*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monetary Human resources Policy Goods/Services Technology Knowledge Others 	<p>Discuss the different types of interaction between stakeholders.</p> <p>Monetary interaction: when there are monetary transactions exchanged between stakeholders.</p> <p>Human Resource interaction: training of personnel and exchanges of such training within the network.</p> <p>Policy interaction: when there are policy-making contributions and exchanges of policy documents between stakeholders, particularly between public authorities and other stakeholders.</p> <p>Technology interaction: when there are exchanges of technology equipments/kits between stakeholders.</p> <p>Knowledge interaction: when there are exchanges of knowledge between stakeholders, particularly between universities/research institutes and other stakeholders.</p> <p>And then a more detailed interaction explanation is necessary – for instance, what kind of scientific ITS knowledge is transferred from the Universities in Europe to the National governments or the European Commission; or what kind of ITS services the ITS providers offer to the public authorities (governments)?</p>
Cost structure*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tangible costs and resource needs Intangible costs and resources 	<p>Discuss the main cost items of the case study (operational costs, investment costs, etc.). Any financial information the stakeholder can share with us. Could be costs from their daily operations, costs from the infrastructure used in their activities... anything we can use. Should be relative to the case study.</p> <p>Tangible costs and resource needs (financial investments or operating capital; time and materials; facilities and equipment; projects at different stages of implementation; market barriers for implementation; commercial products...);</p> <p>Intangible costs and resources: (R&D activities; high-end skilled workforces; human skills and competence; business relationships; brand-identity; media relations; lobbying activities; incentives to innovate (enablers); advertising and management structure);</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Target Market Segment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATIS • ATMS • ATPS • APTS • CVS 	Specify all the possible market segments of the case study and justify the selection (See D2.1 for details) based on its characteristics, behaviour and requirements
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B • B2C • Others 	<p>Discuss the type of marketing strategy</p> <p>B2B: ITS services/products of a business marketed/sold to other businesses.</p> <p>B2C: ITS services/products are marketed/sold to the final consumer by the business.</p>
Revenue model*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue stream • Price targets • Profit margins 	Any financial information the stakeholder can share with us about their income. Where they receive their money from, which are their main sources of income (might be in % if they dont want to give specific data)
Impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic • Social • Environment 	<p>Discuss and quantify the impacts realised by the case study based on the items in the left cell. (e.g. Societal - 10% reduction in traffic accidents, 20% reduction in traffic jams; Environmental – 13% reduction in emissions, etc.).</p> <p>The improvement must be clearly stated by specifying what the situation was before and after implementation (actual/expected) according to the defined KPIs.</p>
KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment • Benefit 	<p>KPI criterion – the extent to which the ITS service meets its defined objectives – expected impact</p> <p>Discuss the key performance indicators used to evaluate the case study. (See D2.2)</p> <p>Deployment KPIs (D2.2) are related to the extent by which ITS services are implemented. Examples include the percentage of road network using various types of ITS services and the percentage of vehicles with intelligent vehicle features (AECOM, 2015)</p> <p>Benefit KPIs (D2.2) are related to the (desired) impacts of ITS services. Examples include the percentage change in journey times, accident rates or CO₂ emissions along routes once ITS have been implemented (AECOM, 2015)</p>
Timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term • Medium term • Long term 	Discuss the timing of the case study
Market viability*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need • Demand • Acceptability 	<p>Describe the market vision by identifying the market needs and demands</p> <p>Need – identify potential users and their interest, TTRANS – “A detected requirement that in the future (in short or medium term) will be demanded by the market, but at this moment is not “necessary” to provide the current services or functionalities in the sector.”</p> <p>Demand – TTRANS – “A requirement requested by the market to improve their</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

		solutions, is an expectation that the market expects with more or less urgency to enrich the services.”
Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional • Economic • Technical • Organisational • Social and attitudes • Impact • Other 	Discuss the main barriers for the case study according to the categories defined in D2.2
Enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional • Economic • Technical • Organisational • Social and attitudes • Impact • Other 	Discuss the main enablers for the case study according to the categories defined in D2.2

Appendix 2 Completed taxonomy fiches of case studies

Appendix 2.1 CS1 Taxonomy fiche

C-ITS platform to coordinate different routers	
Description	
Objectives	<p>The project objectives rely mainly on two aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency (energy, level of service) • Environmental issues (reducing CO2 and pollutant) <p>These objectives are pursued by information sharing mechanism in a competitive/collaborative framework in which a capacity/demand tool suggests</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Routing time-stamp changes preserving confidential business model information at the tactical level, and 4. Mitigation mechanisms issuing real-time routing advice to freight transport companies/truck drivers at the operational level/real time when new bottlenecks would emerge.
Innovation Level	<p>The project exhibits a pilot innovation, since it relies on already commercial decision support tools that must be enhanced with a web service to match the information and feedback time constraints under a consensus reward mechanism.</p>
Innovation Type	<p>The project proposes a breakthrough innovation, since it introduces a new service that can be applied at different geographical levels and implementing different reward policies for the freight transport system.</p> <p>Motorway bottlenecks usually are considered emergent dynamics that cannot be predicted. This fact is partially right when being caused by an accident or an incident between vehicles, however when caused by over demand, instead of emergent dynamic, bottlenecks should be considered un-modelled dynamic. The new service relies on enhancing commercial ITS solutions with the cooperation capacity to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predict over-demanded zones: Road freight transport companies use fleet planners to generate the “optimal route” to each truck. At present, this information is relevant only for the transport company, however the causal analysis of these isolated routes is an excellent source of information to identify and predict over-demanded zones and its interdependencies. • Mitigation mechanisms: A demand-capacity balance mechanism to suggest time-stamp changes or re-routing options under a reward mechanism to transform “queuing” by “waiting” truck operations. <p>The service will be complemented by a tracking functionality for real-time advice issuance, but also to improve the robustness of the solutions.</p> <p>This new service should be implemented considering fairness, transparency and equity criteria to engage freight transport companies in this cooperative ITS framework.</p> <p>This approach opens a new market in which router cooperation/competition mechanisms could support new routing solutions in which transport costs would be reduced considerably. Currently, present routers do not interact at all. They only receive time-space constraints to avoid bottlenecks.</p>
Type of Stakeholders	<p>The project involves various stakeholders' categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government: Should encourage/reward the use of the proposed service to improve freight transport performance without new road investments. • Universities/Research Institutes: new cooperation/competition routing algorithms that would improve the robustness of proposed solution (consider the importance of uncertainties in road transport). • Transport Operator: Freight transport companies. • ITS service provider: Routing algorithms (Aslogic)

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road Operator: Monitoring the flow of trucks engaged with the solution proposed to implement reward mechanisms. • Regulatory Body: New regulations to enhance the use of the service are required to reach a critical mass. • Public/Transport Authority: Elaboration of reward mechanisms. • Roads authority (National, Regional, Local): Validation of service impact and benefits. • European Commission: Funds to support implementation and deployment of the solution proposed. • End users: Freight transport companies, truck drivers • ICT service provider: Cloud information management platform.
Project Initiator	Public: The project should be developed in an EU framework considering the scope of the service and the critical mass required to succeed.
Scope	
Transport Mode	Only road transport mode. It must be considered that a similar service already exists in the aeronautical transport mode.
Transport Type	Freight: The main control will be on freight transport in which personal transport demand will be considered passive. A future extension of the project could consider also personal transport.
Geographic coverage	Motorway: Service could be applied at regional, national or European level. Worthwhile to mention that impact measurement and coordination action will be at local level, cooperation benefits can be achieved at higher geographical aggregation levels.
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic management: Tactical demand capacity balance. • Freight services: Reduction of the travel time by mitigating the number of bottlenecks caused by a spatio-temporal concentration of trucks in one area. • Routing: A passive mechanism for routing interoperability. • Environmental Protection: Reduction of the amount of CO₂ impact and fuel burning. • Road user charging: New reward mechanisms should be considered as a mechanism to reach a critical mass of end-users.
Technology	
Communication	The service will employ long range communication channels (3G/4G and GPS tracking) for issuing real-time routing advice and tracking respectively. Also, a service oriented architecture (SOA) with a peculiar data exchange protocol to support the flow of data with different routers distributed in other systems or central units.
Sensing	Camera: To be used for monitoring purposes in real time.
Hardware	<p>Central: Centralised traffic management system to compute at tactical level spatio-temporal constraints to be issued to freight transport companies under a fairness and equity policy.</p> <p>Personal: To check if constraints will be preserved and take some corrective decisions to be notified through mobile phones, tablets, personal navigation devices, and other hand-held devices.</p>
Decision	<p>Algorithm: Analysis of freight transport demand shared by routers together with traffic patterns to identify bottlenecks and its interdependencies. Computation of spatio-temporal constraints.</p> <p>Simulation will be used to predict the effects of the mitigation mechanisms and to support transparency among end-users.</p>
Business Model	
Product	Intangible: Website service in which routers will connect through SOA mechanism.
Infrastructure financing	Public-Private: The full system could be implemented as a cloud service that could be supported by private financing. The monitoring capacity with road cameras would require public financing.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Operation financing	Public: At technological level, it is not envisaged an important risk in the implementation, however, benefits will depend on the critical mass and the policies implemented. No private companies would like to take the implementation risk if stakeholder engagement is not guaranteed.
Management of network	Policies implemented for the mitigation mechanism should be a consensus between private-public partnership.
Stakeholder grouping*	<p>Public Traffic Administration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role: Formulate and publish traffic regulation. Provide general traffic data. Validate spatio-temporal constraints for the reward mechanisms. • Objectives: Minimise traffic jams Enhance an efficient flow of trucks • Needs: New monitoring tools to verify KPI's. Networking framework with other traffic administration to have a better coordination mechanism to develop appropriate regulations • Input: Data from data providers • Output: Traffic regulation Reward mechanisms <p>Freight Transport Company</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role: Transportation of freight Issues routing demands • Objectives: Minimise transportation time and costs Avoid traffic jams • Needs: New Decision Support Tools to predict and identify jams and find alternative routes. A transparent monitoring mechanism to trust the system. • Input: Time-stamp routes To preserve business model confidentiality, the flow of information will be restricted to spatio-temporal constraints. • Output: Freight services <p>Router Company</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role: Manage traffic data in order to compute robust schedules. • Objectives: Design routes that minimize transportation time and costs • Needs:

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<p>Adapt the algorithms considering spatio-temporal constraints Research in the optimization and simulation arena</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input: Transport demand Motorway time-zones capacity delivery requirements • Output: Mitigation mechanisms that satisfy spatio-temporal constraints High level description of routes, without relevant information on customers (i.e. initial and end point of the route).
Stakeholder interaction*	<p>Policy interaction: Capacity-demand policy requires of smart win-to-win policies that should allow end-users satisfy their own transport hard-constraints (i.e. Delivery time) while adapting routes considering soft-constraints (delivery sequences). Knowledge interaction: Different traffic patterns will require different mitigation mechanism. It is essential to collect previous expertise when issuing capacity constraints. Trust: A regulation policy could benefit some private companies while penalizing others. To really succeed with the proposed service a transparency mechanism should be provided to truly be engaged in the system.</p>
Cost structure*	<p>Operational Costs: A scalability problem could arise once critical mass is reached. Bottleneck interdependencies require a full European network analysis instead of a regional analysis. Since cloud services will be used, no important investment cost is expected, except for the monitoring which could require some road cameras. Tangible costs and resource needs: The full implementation of the service together with validation exercises at regional level could require a team composed by five software engineers (project leader, mathematical modeller, a GIS expert and two senior developers) during 2 years. It is not considered the cost of adapting routers interfaces by the end-users. Intangible costs and resources: Bottleneck interdependencies, demand-capacity balance algorithms have already been implemented at research level in different domains, however, it is expected that some R&D efforts will be required to reach optimal results. Thus, at preliminary level no excessive costs are expected by assuming that present coordination policies could provide acceptable (non-optimal) results.</p>
Target Market Segment	<p>ATIS: The service will use In-vehicle route and navigation systems to react to non-compliant spatio-temporal constraints. ATMS: It contributes to Demand and access management. And can be enhanced with Traffic monitoring services. Also, it contributes to Schedule optimization and Optimized fleet management ATPS: It contributes to Congestion pricing through reward mechanisms.</p>
Type	<p>B2B: ITS services that can be sold to router developer and ERP companies. B2C: ITS services that can be sold to freight transport companies.</p>
Revenue model*	<p>It is envisaged a price target mechanism sold under a pay-per-use policy complemented with a public subsidiary compensation according to benefits measured.</p>
Impacts	<p>Impacts are generally positive, since it is envisaged results in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic: x% fuel reduction, x% truck reduction, x% driver's reduction, x% travel time reduction and in consequence x% maintenance fleet cost reduction. • Social: Road bottleneck mitigation at traffic perspective, and queuing to waiting benefits at human factors perspective (driver stress). • Environmental: emission reduction
KPIs	<p>Benefits have to be estimated as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emission reductions - Reduction of n° of road bottlenecks - Variation of travel time <p>The engagements of local authorities and freight companies at regional level will be supported by a simulation model in which the KPI's proposed will be computed considering different win-to-win policies.</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<p>Deployment KPIs Operational efficiency, Environmental, Continuity of traffic and freight management ITS Services, Linking the vehicle with the transport infrastructure</p> <p>Benefit KPIs Network efficiency & congestion, Improve Environmental Impacts, Increased capacity and operational efficiency, Reduced environmental and energy impacts Increased productivity and for motor carriers and service providers, Increased comfort and convenience of travel</p>
Timing	Medium-Term business: Once deployed, it is expected 1 or 2 years to reach the critical mass to measure real benefits.
Market viability*	<p>Need: Real end-users should be freight transport companies and router developers.</p> <p>Demand: It is considered as a next step of present routers: minimum cooperation mechanism to avoid unnecessary spatio-temporal coexistence of trucks in the same area.</p>
Barriers	<p>Organisational: The main barrier is essentially the lack of cooperation between stakeholders, since private freight companies that are competing in the same market should start cooperating under a win-to-win approach.</p> <p>Institutional: New policies/regulations for pricing (tolls), usage, and compliance.</p>
Enablers	<p>Impact: Europe re-industrialization requires of new efficient road surface transport infrastructure, in which transport time and cost should be reduced to a competitive value. The minimization of motorway bottlenecks through an information sharing platform and small time-stamp or re-routing adjustments seems to provides the right solution envisaged by traffic authorities and drivers. ("Reindustrialising Europe: the issues at stake in a European Innovation and Industrial Policy", http://www.robert-schuman.eu/en/doc/questions-d-europe/qe-256-en.pdf)</p>

Appendix 2.2 CS2 Taxonomy fiche

Compass4D – Verona Case Study	
Description	
Objective	<p>The project objectives rely mainly on three aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety issues • Efficiency (energy, level of service) • Environmental issues (reducing CO2 and pollutant) <p>These objectives are pursued by improving the urban traffic performances through improving driving behaviours and control systems, thanks to a specific cooperative-ITS implementation.</p>
Innovation Level	The project exhibits a close-to-market innovation, since it exhibits solutions that can be easily replicated.
Innovation Type	<p>The project proposes a radical innovation, since it introduces new services and implements for the first time in Italy a cooperative-ITS solution.</p> <p>New services in the city of Verona consist in</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Road Hazard Warning (RHW) - Road Works Warning - Speed advisory (GLOSA system) - Red light violation warning - Transit speed improving through signal priority (TSP) <p>RHW System aims to prevent collisions in case of abnormal or blind queues, and Road Works Warning aims to prevent similar circumstances. Speed Advisory instead aims to improve driving behaviours due to prevent vehicles stopping at red lights: the objective is to make more smooth the traffic stream, reducing energy consumption and pollution, but also improving mean speed while reducing peak speed which can be useful also to improve road safety; moreover the same technology is useful to prevent red light violations, but also to detect it.</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	Finally, the system also provides for transit signal priority (TSP) which can be seen as an additional service oriented to transit operator that can be translated into additional benefit for the final users.
Type of Stakeholders	The project involves various stakeholders' categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public authority: The Municipality of Verona • Urban Transit operator • Citizens: the users of Verona mobility system • Automotive supplier: Audi • OEMs: SWARCO • ICT service provider: Telecom Italia
Project initiator	The project is developed into an EU CIP framework
Scope	
Transport Mode	Only road transport modes
Transport Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal transport • Public transport
Geographic coverage	Core application is the implementation of a Platform capable to delivery GLOSA service for the whole signalized urban road network in Verona, including both centralized and isolated junctions. The Verona controlled network has more than 150 junctions.
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road Safety • Traffic Management
Technology	
Communication	<p>Cooperative-ITS real-time messages can both run on short-range and long-range communication systems.</p> <p>Short range system is based on ETSI-G5 standard (a 5Ghz Wireless LAN standard for ITS application), and provides separately information about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic Light Assistant • Traffic Information • Road Works Warning <p>The Traffic Light Assistant uses SPAT/MAP standard for encoding and broadcasting information about junctions' topologies and regulation parameters, while "Event Information", such as Traffic Information and Road Works Warning, uses CAM-DEMN format to broadcast information to vehicle. Communications runs between roadside units (one for a single junction) and on-board-units (OBUs).</p> <p>Long-range system is based, for the first time in Europe, on a 4G platform which links the central unit (TMS) and the users' mobile devices (which have to run a specific software app).</p> <p>In-vehicle information reach the driver with a delay <3s</p> <p>System central unit is also capable to use DATEX protocol to exchange data with other systems or central units.</p>
Sensing	More than 30 cameras
Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central unit • Roadside units (>=25) • Short-Range type Driver units: G5-OBU (Audi self-equipped vehicles, buses, other vehicles....) (>=20) • Long-Range type Driver units: common mobile devices/tablets with specific software app (30 users are involved in test-activities)
Decision	Decision procedure is based both on algorithms and simulation.
Business Model	
Product	Tangible
Infrastructure financing	Public

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Operation financing	Since the project is carried on under a EU CIP co-financing, it requires 50% of costs covered by the beneficiaries.
Management of Network	Public
Stakeholder grouping	The relations with transport companies involved in the pilot (ATV, Taxi company, etc.) were maintained primarily through Verona Municipality. Swarco Mizar was the point of contact for all technical issues related to Verona Pilot and providing updated status information about the overall project to the City and additional Transport Companies.
Stakeholder interaction	Face-to-face meeting with local stakeholders were organized with monthly frequency in Verona. The Decision-Making Process scheme has been designed to the explicit aim of including citizens and all the stakeholders in decision activities.
Cost structure	Initial investment cost has been reported as € 360.000, while annual operational cost has been estimated as € 24.000. Based on such evaluation, the annual minimum revenue was estimated in € 68.384,74: this is the amount that would allow the service to run without any monetary loss, making the Net Present Value (NPV) of the service for a period of 10 years equal to zero. The same NPV could be used to quantify the minimum required environmental gain, e.g. in term of pollutants' social cost reduction.
Target Market Segment	ITS application into this project relies on cooperative-ITS category, involving I2V communications. Adoption of specifications and standards and Vehicle-to-Vehicle communications are not in the scope of the project. The implementation also involves a Advanced Traffic Management System (ATMS) and provides an Advanced Traveller Information System (ATIS).
Type	Business-To-Consumer
Revenue Model	Despite some of the most important outcomes of the project are to evaluate in terms of pollutant and social costs reduction, a specific money revenue during operations can be found and explained highlighting the specific application of TSP (Transit Signal Priority), while this kind of feature is capable to improve public transport performances affecting positively the modal split and reducing the productive costs. However, other clear incomes are associated especially with the system-providing activities. In this case especially the OEM, but also the ICT service provider, have specific money gains as they provide hardware and services to public authority and operators.
Impacts	Impacts are generally positive, since the implementation resulted in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stops reduction: 15% (simulated data) • Travel time -7% • Road Safety: it's improved due to smoothed driving behaviour • Energy: smoother journeys can be translated in an energy consumption reduction • Environmental: emission reduction due to reduction of Stop/ Start
KPIs	Benefits have to be estimated as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emission reductions - Reduction of n° of stops - Variation of travel time - Accident reduction <p>Regarding the emissions reduction, some consideration could be carried on.</p> <p>The annual passenger travel time and CO2 emissions for Verona are ex-ante estimated in 22594 hours per person per year and 63610 tons/year of total CO2.</p> <p>Considering that the social cost of CO2 emissions is 120€/ton, the equivalent of the estimated minimum annual revenue of € 68.384 is roughly 570 tons of CO2.</p> <p>This represents approximately 0.9% of the annual CO2 emissions of the City of Verona, and this number could be interpreted as the reduction of CO2 emissions that could make sustainable the project just from CO2 emissions point of view.</p> <p>Benefits have been proved thanks to two different evaluation applications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulation application • Direct measurements <p>The simulation application was driven through different scenarios considering various</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<p>sensitive parameters (penetration rate, communication delay, traffic demand) in order to determine the impact of the services on both drivers (travel times, fuel consumptions, number of stops) and municipality (traffic flow).</p> <p>Direct measurements have been carried on during one year, collecting data from both vehicles and intersections, but unfortunately the data-granularity was not fully suitable to directly evaluate the pollutant emission, since the sampling-interval-resolution on monitored vehicles resulted insufficient to seize their cinematic transients, which are important for understanding pollutant emission dynamics: poor sampled data needed to be interpolated.</p>
Timing	Medium-term-Business
Market viability	The services have shown to be accepted and well evaluated by final users, since they allow to improve safety and mean speed, and to reduce driving stress. Also, public authority and operators showed to be interested about implementing this kind of services.
Barriers	The main barrier is essentially operational, and it regards privacy issues related to communications. During the Compass4D pilot a large amount of data has been collected in order to evaluate benefits of the system: some of the data will potentially need to identify vehicle and/or the driver. The raw data has been treated as confidential and collected and organized in databases allocated according to inter-operational standards (DATEX II, ETSI, etc.).
Enablers	The Municipality participation have been very important, showing to be experienced about European projects. The city was yet equipped with an OMNIA platform controlling more than 150 junctions, and other systems/technologies (for urban traffic control, etc).

Appendix 2.3 CS3 Taxonomy fiche

SIEEG Case study	
Description	
Objective	<p>The two main objectives of the project are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased efficiency of container transport from deep sea terminals to the hinterland • Higher security at inland terminals <p>The Secure Information Exchange Extended Gate (SIEEG) concept improves the efficiency and security of the transport from deep sea terminals to inland terminals and hinterland (abroad).</p> <p>Sub-objectives and underlying objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of profitability for stakeholders • Use of sensor technology to increase the exchange of better and more trustworthy information in the hinterland chain • To create a public extended gate with the best available infrastructure for a secure lane • Increase the attractiveness of inland waterway transport
Innovation Level	The project is out of the demonstration phase and is deployed by Combi Terminal Twente B.V. (CTT) together with its partners amongst others Bolk Transport (logistics service provider)
Innovation Type	<p>The project proposes a differential type of innovation.</p> <p>The container transport efficiency on an existing link is improved. The innovation of the project is the establishment of a secure information extended gate functionality, using integrated and synchronized data exchange between terminals and shippers through an open IT platform.</p> <p>The SIEEG functionality consists of a web service which gives insight into relevant data regarding the handling and transportation of goods 24/7. At the location of the inland terminal CTT the IT platform is supplemented with data from the registration and security zone at the Multi-Modal Terminal.</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Project initiator	The demonstration project was initiated by Combi Terminal Twente B.V. (CTT) and supported by Dutch Institute for advanced logistics (Dinalog, nowadays part of TKI Dinalog). The objective of TKI Dinalog is to structurally facilitate public-private partnerships in the area of research within the Top Sector Logistics.
Type of Stakeholders	The project involves various stakeholders. Direct stakeholders (project partners) in the project are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Container terminals • Transport companies (inland waterways and road) • University • IT-service provider Indirect stakeholders are <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shippers • Skippers and truck drivers • Port authorities • Customs
Scope	
Transport Mode	Road and inland waterways.
Transport Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private transport
Geographic coverage	The demonstration project was focussed on the link Rotterdam – Hengelo (NL).
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased efficiency of container transport from deep sea terminals to the hinterland; saving time and costs • Higher security at inland terminals • Increase of profitability for stakeholders • Use of sensor technology to increase the exchange of better and more trustworthy information in the hinterland chain • To create a public extended gate with the best available infrastructure for a secure lane • Increase the attractiveness of inland waterway transport
Technology	
Communication	SIEEG is a web-based service that allows logistics agents to monitor data about handling and transportation of goods. The following communication is active: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At the inland terminal, GPS is used to have trucks automatically report to the terminal; geofencing (long range) • The truck registers through optical character recognition and hand scan (short range) • Ship movements are followed by public AIS data (long range) • Transport planning data are made available between logistic partners
Sensing	Hundreds of sensors
Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized communication platform for data exchange • GPS trucks; geofencing at inland terminal • AIS on inland waterway ships • Optical character recognition (OCR): For identification of cargo • Hand scan: identification of truck driver at terminal
Decision	Decision procedure is based both on algorithms.
Business Model	
Product	Intangible (information service)
Infrastructure financing	Private.
Operation financing	Private
Management	Private
Stakeholder grouping	Role: Inland container terminal CTT is the initiator. Bolk transport Almelo and Burger Logistics are transport partners in the logistic chain. Inland terminal MCS Meppel is partner

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<p>to advise on knowledge transfer to other terminals. University Twente delivered ICT knowledge. Dinalog had a monitoring role and subsidized the project (public private financier)</p> <p>Interest/ objectives: The main objective of CTT is to create an efficient extended gate functionality in Enschede for the Port of Rotterdam with the same service and security level as in the port of Rotterdam.</p> <p>Needs: Data sharing, development of algorithms for effective data sharing</p> <p>Input: Logistics data and public data (amongst others ship positioning)</p> <p>Outputs: Logistics data</p>
Stakeholder interaction	<p>Knowledge interaction (Algorithms for data sharing and data).</p> <p>Human resource interaction (coordination of planning consequences between employees at stakeholder operational level)</p>
Costs	Total project budget € 1,172,00, of which € 250,000 funded for research for the project has been subsidized by Dinalog
Target Market Segment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travel information systems: Travel information is given to inland skippers via the developed application. • Transport management systems: The web based service share information of shippers and logistic service providers to optimize transport efficiency • Payment systems: Geofencing and the automatic security check can be seen as a form of a payment system
Type	Business-To-Business
Revenue model	
Impacts	<p>Economic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time reduction in gate entry of trucks from 10.5 minutes to 65 seconds • 2500 extra containers transported • € 50-75 higher benefits per truck per day (faster gate entrance) <p>Social</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better and more trustworthy information available between partners <p>Environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modal shift from road to inland waterways • 32% CO2 reduction
KPIs	<p>Deployment KPIs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of stakeholders in the logistic chain informed about SIEEG <p>Benefit KPIs (implicitly formulated in goals)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Created jobs - Effective data sharing via IT-platform measured as % of data exchange requests covered by the developed IT platform. - Increase of in transshipment volume of high value goods. - Transshipment time of trucks at the terminal - Cost reduction per truck movement at CTT - CO₂ reduction (per container?) on link Rotterdam Hengelo
Timing	The demonstration project run from 2011-2014. The SIEEG functionality is still used CTT. There are/ has been other project for further dissemination of the project results.
Market viability	Need: Other inland terminal are interested in the SIEEG functionality
Barriers	<p>Technical: To find/ create an application programming interface (API) to synchronize heterogeneous information and to securely exchange it between partners.</p> <p>Organisational: Stakeholder information (availability of data from deep see terminal)</p>
Enablers	<p>Technical: technical knowledge within the consortium of stakeholders</p> <p>Organisational: perseverance of project partners to integrate the different contribution of suppliers</p>

Appendix 2.4 CS4 Taxonomy fiche

KEEP SAFE: A Knowledge-based approach to understanding railway safety	
Description	
Objectives	<p>The project addressed the following challenges within the railway industry:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety of passengers, staff and communities • Relationship between data security and railway safety • Predictive maintenance of railway infrastructure. <p>These three areas were addressed by collecting knowledge from a range of areas across the industry to understand the relationships between railway data and railway safety. A series of knowledge models were created to support data-driven decision making.</p>
Innovation Level	Despite being a pilot study, the project exhibits a close-to-market innovation. The solution can be replicated and is currently being applied by a consortium of all key players across the British railway industry under the leadership of Coventry University.
Innovation Type	<p>When considered in the wider context of transport this project represents a differential innovation as it combines aspects already in use in sectors such as aerospace and to some extent automotive in order to apply its benefits in the context of the railway industry.</p> <p>However, when looked from the perspective of the railway industry as a separate part of the transport sector, this project represents a radical innovation. This is because the project paved the way for practical implementations such as the turning of every train into an infrastructure monitoring train for the purpose of predictive maintenance. In this case, with support from a major train manufacturer, a train owner and a train operator company in the UK, this vehicle-to-infrastructure system has adopted the principles of KEEP SAFE to fit a number of sensors in trains to measure the overhead electrification system for the purpose of informing a predictive maintenance strategy that ultimately results in an improved safety.</p>
Project initiator	The project was originally funded by the UK Railway Safety and Standards Board (RSSB) and a follow-up consortium is funded by a H2020 project entitled 'Transforming Transport' of which Network Rail is a key partner in charge of the pilot. Network Rail, investing some private funds too, launched an enhanced pilot including a range of partners. Coventry University is part of the Network Rail consortium and leads the part that deals with data analysis.
Type of Stakeholders	<p>The project involves various categories of stakeholders.</p> <p>From within the railway industry:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Train manufacturers: Alstom Transport • Train owners: Network Rail • Train operators: Virgin Trains • Railway regulatory bodies: Office of Rail Regulation <p>From outside the industry:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government: Railway Safety and Standards Board • Citizens: ultimately beneficiaries from an increased safety
Scope	
Transport Mode	Railway Transport
Transport Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public • Freight
Geographic coverage	The core idea developed by the project is not limited to a specific geographic domain. However, its specific implementations can be applied with different degrees of geographic spread.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	In particular, a current implementation focuses on the application of the principles in a section of the British railway referred to as London-North West, which extends from London to Manchester in the UK.
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety • Predictive maintenance of infrastructure
Technology	
Communication	<p>The core idea developed by the project relies on a short-range communication mainly between experts from across the domain.</p> <p>Specific implementations such as the one being applied in the London-North West section of the British railway relies on both a short-range and wide-range communication. In addition to expert knowledge elicitation (face to face) workshops, the initiative relies on the collection of data from trains running across a large distance and the communication of that data via WAN for its processing at Coventry University.</p>
Sensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellite for location • Cameras for video recording • Sensors for factors including speed, vertical force, longitudinal acceleration, height.
Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central units in train and in particular locations • Sensors in trains
Decision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision procedures based on both algorithms
Business Model	
Product	<p>The main product is a method, therefore intangible.</p> <p>Its applications require tangible assets and offer tangible results: information to aid decision making.</p>
Infrastructure financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public • Private
Operation financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public • Private
Management of network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public by the Railway Safety and Standards Board • Private by Network Rail
Stakeholder grouping*	<p>The original idea as funded by the Railway Safety and Standards Board relied on a group of stakeholders from across the railway industry which was managed by Coventry University.</p> <p>The implementation that followed is delivered by a specific consortium formed and financed by Network Rail, which also includes Alstom Transport, Virgin Trains and Serco.</p>
Stakeholder interaction*	<p>Stakeholders in the current implementation interact on a regular basis to provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical knowledge • Financial support • Data collected • Testing and validation of results • Use of the outcomes of the project
Cost structure*	<p>The cost of the initial project as funded by the Railway Safety and Standards Board was £35,000 of UK public funding.</p> <p>The practical implementation that followed is being funded by Network Rail at a cost of £50,000 of private funding for the data analysis part alone.</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Target Market Segment	ITS application of the principles developed by this project relies on the cooperative-ITS category. It involves I2V communications for the purpose of data collection and subsequent analysis.
Type	Business to Business approach, with the ultimate aim of benefitting both business and consumers.
Impacts	<p>The main impacts of this project are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social: An improved safety has a direct impact on society and their perception of the railway. • Economic: The benefits of application of the project findings lead to direct economic benefits in terms of predictive maintenance and consistency of the service.
KPIs	<p>In terms of deployment, the main KPIs are related to the success of the practical implementations of the principles developed by this project. Benefits in the context of the current implementation by Network Rail are perceived as follows:</p> <p>Increased safety, leading to:</p> <p>Positive social impact</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved customer satisfaction • Improved levels of compliance • Improved business performance <p>Reduction of unplanned maintenance and repairs, leading to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less cancellations and delays • An increased availability of service • Increase customer satisfaction • Improved levels of compliance • Improved business performance
Timing	Medium term impact due to the need to fit new sensors as needed and collect data.
Market viability*	<p>There is a clear need in the context of the UK railway industry for initiatives supporting both predictive maintenance and improved safety.</p> <p>In terms of demand, the alternative currently in place is not sufficient to provide acceptable levels of performance, hence the adoption of this solution by major players within the industry.</p> <p>Acceptability has been significant for the initiative currently being implemented.</p>
Barriers	<p>Main barriers included, in this order:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need to fit sensors for the collection of data, which is an engineering modification and therefore takes time and resources (technical) • Availability of data (technical) • Stakeholders' readiness to share their data (institutional, attitude) • Different views of safety, depending on the stakeholder and the nature of their business (social, organisational)
Enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of the subject areas (data and safety) across the transport sector and the railway industry in particular (Institutional, Impact) • Current regulations (Institutional) • Social impact of an increased safety performance (Social and attitude) • Current developments in the digital domain (Economic, Organisational) • Relevance of the project towards the priorities of the Railway Industry in their long term strategy (Impact)

Appendix 2.5 ACS1 Taxonomy fiche

University VAOPoint Mobility	
Description	
Objectives	<p>VAOPoint provides a solution for the growing demand on sustainable intercity mobility in European countries. VAOPoint offers an effective intelligent carpooling service for daily intercity mobility, where users can access numerous carpooling offers. In addition to traditional cost saving on sharing transportation expenses, VAOPoint will promote the reduction of users' carbon footprint and decrease traffic congestion by promoting high-occupancy vehicles.</p> <p>The pilot VAOPoint took place at the Autonomous University of Barcelona who has a mobility plan promoting collective transport, journeys by bicycles as well as achieving more rational use of private vehicles matching the goals of VAOPoint.</p> <p>The project objectives rely mainly on three aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency: Matching users to vehicles that minimize trajectory deviations and maximize economic efficiency. • Comfort: Encourage social preferences matching, avoid campus pathway bottlenecks and guarantee parking availability. • Environmental issues: Reduce the carbon footprint (CO₂) and pollutants as a result of the reduction in the number of cars used. <p>These objectives have been validated in a University (UAB) mobility environment by increasing the car occupancy factor, and in consequence reducing the number of vehicles accessing to campus facilities through different control systems, in which a real-time information sharing mechanism is critical for the robustness and resilience of the ITS service.</p>
Innovation Level	<p>VAOPoint is a pilot project that offers a carpooling ITS application in its first city trial/deployment to members of the University community for access to the campus.</p> <p>As an environment with high levels of daily influx of private vehicles, the UAB Bellaterra campus get filled up with over 13,000 vehicles of a very low occupation index: 1.2 people per vehicle - the same average as that of the metropolitan region of Barcelona. Increasing the average occupation and achieving a rational use of the car is one of the stakeholder's objectives.</p>
Innovation Type	<p>The project proposes a differential innovation, since it introduces a new service in an existing market that can reduce the flow of vehicles into the University campus, but also can be applied to other transit scenarios with similar problems such as industrial parks.</p> <p>The final product will include several mechanisms which will detect high-occupation vehicles from those which are not, by using consented and anonymised geolocation, cameras in car parks, etc.</p> <p>The new service relies on providing a carpooling ITS solution with the geo-localization to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjust the time-stamp matching point: 4G Communication and tracking are key to engage end-users and reach a critical mass for an efficient service. • Access control to facilities: Real time computation to validate the use of parking areas. • Compute reward mechanisms: 4G Communication and tracking is critical to engage end-users in a reward competition such as guaranteed access to campus parking lot, so as to avoid the use of direct contact through alternative social networks. <p>At present, several universities are supporting the use of carpooling services to tackle the everyday bottlenecks in campus facilities. Lack of geo-localization and 4G communication in most commercial services lead to poor acceptability by the users and the university mobility managers.</p>
Type of Stakeholders	<p>The project involves various stakeholders' categories: Existing stakeholders</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City: University governing body that make decisions regarding the territorial management of the infrastructure, facilities, and services within the campus. A typical university campus shows the same logistic problems as small cities; UAB management. • Universities/Research Institutes: Present services can be extended with clustering approaches considering socio-technological aspects; UAB dept. of Telecommunications and Systems, Engineering, Living lab - CORE Smart and Sustainable Cities research network • ITS service provider: Aslogic. • Transport Authority: The university mobility department. • European Commission: Funded through the FrontierCities EU-FP7 project which supports SMEs and start-ups to develop Smart Mobility applications for cities across Europe. • End users: Students and university employees. • ITS association: CRUE • Others: Websays (Social media marketing company) <p>Potential stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT service provider: Tracking and communication (Fleet mobile, Tom-tom) services. • City: Barcelona and Sabadell municipalities
Project Initiator	Private: The project was initiated by an SME, a University spin-off company Aslogic
Transport Mode	Only road transport mode. For those campuses with a poor public transport system, multimodal could be considered.
Transport Type	Personal: Students and employee's mobility is considered.
Geographic coverage	Urban and Motorway: Service can be applied at urban areas but also at metropolitan level for those Universities with a remote campus.
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic management: Tactical demand capacity balance. • Parking: Real time information about available free parking areas for HOV. • Public Transport: New public transport services for intra-campus mobility. • Environmental Protection: Reduction of the amount of CO₂ impact and fuel burning.
Communication	<p>Short range – Wi-Fi suitable for V2I technology is used to validate access to university facilities such as parking areas to granted HOV drivers.</p> <p>Long range – 4G communication is used to support Cellular networks for real-time matching purposes.</p>
Sensing	The service relies mainly on smart soft-sensors, for matching, tracking and identification purposes, however some cameras are optionally used at parking areas for validation purposes.
Hardware	<p>Central: University centralised mobility management system to compute at tactical level a matching process between users and drivers.</p> <p>Personal: Personal mobile phones required for tracking purposes.</p> <p>Roadside: Soft sensor at parking areas for validation purposes. Main V2I communication is implemented by tracking mechanisms.</p>
Decision	<p>Algorithm: Computation of demand-capacity matching algorithms considering socio-technological indicators.</p> <p>Simulation is used to predict the effects of public transport services for intra-campus mobility.</p>
Product	Intangible: Website service in which users and drivers will fit mobility demand.
Infrastructure financing	Public: University management body

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Operation financing	Public.
Management of network	Network should be governed initially by the University as a public institution, since private information of students is required to reach the critical mass, and university facilities should be used considering university policies. The network could be transferred also to a public-private maintenance and exploitation at future steps.
Stakeholder grouping*	<p>Universities Role: Responsible to manage campus facilities such as pathways and parking areas. Objectives: Increasing the average occupation and achieving a rational use of the car, improve mobility considering sustainability criteria Needs: Reduce the number of vehicles in the campus facilities. Input: Potential end-users and transport preferences. Output: Estimation of parking usage.</p> <p>ITS Service Provider Role: Responsible to maintain the software framework. Objectives: preserve users by providing excellent matchings and supporting rewards. Needs: demand-capacity analysis algorithms considering different metrics. Input: Potential end-users and transport preferences. Output: Matching users with vehicles.</p> <p>University Community Role: End-users. Objectives: cheap, efficient and comfortable mobility system. Needs: Mobility service that fits its preferences. Input: Spatio-temporal preferences. Output: Meeting location information.</p>
Stakeholder interaction*	<p>Monetary interaction: Users will contribute to the transportation cost considering different policies.</p> <p>Policy interaction: Both at National level but also at European level there is a common concern between Universities about mobility policies.</p> <p>Knowledge interaction: Since different universities have been implementing different carpooling services, the results of different pilots and experiences can help to the evolution of present tools.</p>
Cost structure*	<p>Tangible costs and resource needs: The extension of present VAOPOINT service to automate the access to a parking area requires of some devices not yet acquired. Software maintenance at present is considered a recurrent cost that could be shared between university partners. It is not considered the cost of adapting routers to extend the matching service.</p> <p>Intangible costs and resources: Incentive campaigns and reward mechanism must be constantly re-designed and/or adapted to preserve end-users.</p>
Target Market Segment	<p>ATIS: The VAOPOINT service updates at real time parking assignments considering the uncertainties in the traffic and the arrival process.</p> <p>APTS: New public transport facilities for intra-campus mobility.</p> <p>ATPS: It contributes to mobility pricing through reward mechanisms.</p>
Type	<p>B2B: Some reward mechanisms are achieved by B2B benefiting other sectors.</p> <p>B2C: The main mobility service is oriented to particular end-users.</p>
Revenue model*	It is envisaged a price target mechanism sold under a pay-per-use policy complemented with a public subsidiary compensation according to benefits measured.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Impacts	<p>Impacts are generally positive, since it is envisaged results in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic: x% fuel reduction and x% vehicle reduction in campus facilities. • Social: The right penetration of carpooling for university mobility has an indirect penetration in other mobility segments. • Environmental: emission reduction and preservation of green areas.
KPIs	<p>Benefits have to be estimated as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emission reductions - Reduction of n° of vehicles in university campus - Reduction of bottlenecks in campus pathways. <p>Deployment KPIs Operational efficiency, Environmental, Continuity of traffic and Linking the vehicle with the transport infrastructure</p> <p>Benefit KPIs Network efficiency & congestion, Improve Environmental Impacts, Increased capacity and operational efficiency, Reduced environmental and energy impacts Increased comfort and convenience of travel</p> <p>Number of total requests Number of fulfilled requests Number of active users Average occupancy rate Distance travelled</p>
Timing	Short term for deployment.
Market viability*	<p>Need: National and European meetings validates that there is a need to be solved with the use of ITS for every-day student's mobility.</p> <p>Demand: There is a temporal demand for these services, but once the contact is created between users, some of them move to other networking tools. Thus, reward mechanisms are critical to engage end-users.</p>
Barriers	<p>Institutional (Political prioritisation)</p> <p>The initial pilot originally intended as an intercity solution was halted due to the change in political power after the municipal elections in Catalonia. As a result, the project lost institutional support in Barcelona and Sabadell municipalities. Since the pilot project was supported by frontierCities, it was no longer plausible to align the commercial needs/calendar of frontierCities with new rounds of meetings to recover the administration support.</p> <p>Therefore, it was decided to develop and deploy a second version of the platform dedicated to a University community (UAB in this case) having a high influx of private vehicles.</p> <p>Technical (Extension to other markets)/Lack of demonstrated benefits</p> <p>During the stakeholders' meeting with one of the City Councils in Barcelona province, the Mayor indicated that high occupancy vehicle identification is required for extension to industrial districts, and not just a web app only. To the City council, it is a key point for administrations who intend to promote policies to foster the carpooling.</p> <p>Technical: Readiness of the infrastructure (may require an upgrade).</p> <p>Social and attitudes (lack of user acceptance): Another barrier is the lack of user acceptance, since "solo-driver" behaviour requires some incentive campaigns. Reward mechanism should be alive to avoid end-users to exploit the contacts on their own.</p> <p>Organisational: Cooperation between stakeholders</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Enablers	<p>Institutional: Universities want to preserve green areas and other facilities and avoid investing in new parking or pathways.</p> <p>Economic: A highly-occupied vehicle provides a better service and cost than public transport.</p> <p>Technical: FIWARE technology was used, a platform created by the European Union and aimed at providing an open, public and free architecture to help individuals and organisations develop internet-related products in the future.</p> <p>Impact (Proven benefits)</p> <p>The University version of the platform will permit the project initiator (an SME) obtain the first successful case that will increase the credibility in future dealings with City Councils.</p> <p>The UAB mobility department already acquired a first license to evaluate technical issues and to analyse the convenience of how to integrate car-pooling service in their mobility policy (i.e. to reserve parking places for high occupancy vehicles).</p>
----------	---

Appendix 2.6 ACS3 Taxonomy fiche

Case study “sychromodal transport corridor Rotterdam-Limburg”	
Description	
Objective	<p>In the project an ICT platform is being developed in which information in the transport chain from sea going ship - deep sea terminal – inland waterways/ road transport – inland terminal to warehouse is improved. The demonstration project is between deep sea terminal Rotterdam to inland terminals in Limburg. The main objective is to gain more insight in the status of containers from sea to warehouse in the hinterland. This allows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To optimally plan resources and work teams • To reduce slack in the planning; often containers remain on the terminals longer than necessary due to lack of information. • To support sychromodal transport and increase the share of inland waterway transport due to improved planning possibilities. • Reduction of ad-hoc communication
Innovation Level	<p>The project has constructed a demonstrator. Currently the project is in the pilot phase (TRL 7). After the pilot, the project is expected to be implemented by the partners. The ITS/ICT partners can commercialize the service to be integrated in daily operations of the supply chain.</p>
Innovation Type	<p>The project proposes a differential type of innovation.</p> <p>The container transport efficiency on an existing link is improved. The innovation of the project is provision of real time data on container transport on the complete chain from sea to hinterland. It includes the information of sea ships, deep sea terminals, inland waterways, trucks and inland terminals. Eventually this would lead to different decisions that cut out the time slack and speed up the delivery of certain goods dramatically.</p>
Project initiator	<p>Three parties involved in the container supply chain and TNO.</p>
Type of Stakeholders	<p>The case study is based on a demonstration project lead by research institute TNO. The logistic chain serviced consists of a shipper, an inland terminal and a warehouse operator. ITS and ICT companies are involved to deliver ITS/ ICT knowledge, data and the frontend of the platform. Other stakeholders are the deep-sea port authority, a regional network organisation for medium and small enterprises. The project is supported and funded by TKI Dinalog</p>

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Scope	
Transport Mode	Road, maritime shipping and inland shipping.
Transport Type	Freight transport (private) using containers
Geographic coverage	The demonstration project is focussed on the link Rotterdam – Limburg (NL). Involved parties mainly have a national focus.
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased transparency and efficiency of container transport from deep sea terminals to the hinterland • Reduction of transport time from 10 to 3-7 days (ambition) • Better planning of resources/ work teams and less ad-hoc communication • Increase the attractiveness of inland waterway transport
Technology	
Communication	<p>The developed IT platform combines data from Sea ships, sea port, hinterland traffic and inland ports. The following communication is active:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ships (sea and inland waterways) are followed by AIS • Trucks are followed with GPS • Container handling data from the deep-sea terminal are shared with the system • Container handling data at the inland terminal are shared with the system • Planning data of the freight forwarder, inland terminal and shipper are shared
Sensing	AIS, GPS
Hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication platform for data exchange • GPS truck • AIS on inland waterway ships
Decision	The system provides information that can be used by shipper and logistic service providers in the chain. The system does not yet contain active decision support; however, the system allows for better decision making. The system also contains algorithms to estimate time of arrival based on actual traffic information and statistics.
Business Model	
Product	Intangible (information service)
Infrastructure financing	Private.
Operation financing	Private
Management	Private
Stakeholder grouping	The case study is based on a demonstration project lead by institute TNO. Other parties in the project are ICT platform provider, Deep sea port authority, data supplier, Regional network organisation for medium and small enterprises, shipper, Inland terminal. Transport organisation Soft and hardware suppliers.
Stakeholder interaction	<p>Knowledge interaction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TNO shares logistic, ICT and innovation knowledge on the platform development with ICT stakeholders and vice versa. - The regional development company uses its network of companies to create a platform of interested parties. - Lessons learnt during the pilot are published and shared by DIALOG - Several stakeholders share their transport data
Costs	The main costs are related to the development of the platform and operation and maintenance of the service. The development of the service includes adoption of interested parties and the alignment of their activities in developing the service.
Target Market Segment	The case study covers elements of ATIS (Real time information is used to inform operators in the logistics chain to allow them to synchronize their activities) and ATMS (logistic planners receive real time information to improve their planning and optimize e.g. the use of inland shipping).
Type	Business-To-Business
Revenue model	Currently the service is offered for free as it is in the pilot phase. When in operation it is expected that a fee will have to be charged.

D2.3 Case study taxonomy

Impacts	<p>Economic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of transport time of container transport from Rotterdam to warehouse in Hinterland. • Efficient planning of resources and work teams • Improved efficiency in communication between stakeholders in transport chain. • Better service to customers; containers can get priority <p>Social</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better and more trustworthy information available between partners <p>Environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modal shift from road to inland waterways
KPIs	<p>Deployment KPIs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not defined yet: Could be % of containers arriving at warehouse fully tracked by the system; shippers connected; sea ports connected; transporters connected (barge / truck) <p>Benefit KPIs (implicitly formulated in goals)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction in travel time (reduction of 3-7 days' travel time from sea port to warehouse) - % increase in containers transported by inland waterways - number of containers with planning intervention
Timing	The pilot is planned to be finished in February 2018.
Market viability	Need: The ITS/ ICT partners are interested in commercializing the platform developed. Also, other inland terminals are interested in this functionality, especially on integrating data from the deep-sea terminal
Barriers	<p>Technical: Access to real time data with privacy restrictions</p> <p>Organisational: Availability of real time container data with privacy restrictions</p>
Enablers	<p>Technical: development of APIs</p> <p>Organisational: good data governance, parties in business ecosystem</p> <p>Economic: The reduction in slack and better planning of resources.</p>